

The impact of Corporate Social Responsibility Disclosure Decision, Disclosure Quality, Disclosure Quantity, Disclosure Index on Financial Analyst Coverage: Evidence from Financial Times Global 500 Companies

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Abstract

Purpose:

For informational perspective, this study intends to examine how informativeness of corporate non-financial disclosures, as a good surrogate for financial analysts, on financial analysts' properties and behavior that evidenced from standalone corporate sustainability report, released by the top 500 multinational corporations in terms of market capitalization, yearly turnover and profitability, testifying how financial analysts' data drilling and information-producing procedures being influenced by the latest on-rising publication trend, namely corporation social responsibility information.

Methodology:

This study uses OLS regression to examine the impact of CSR disclosures decision, disclosures quantity and disclosures quality on financial analyst coverage. Furthermore, this study will run GMM to robustness of the results. For the disclosure quality, this study will use self-developed research instrument to capture corporate CSR disclosure quality.

Findings:

The results show that firms issue stand-alone CSR reports can attract more financial analysts following the firms. When firms with thirty party assuring their CSR reports also attract more financial analysts following themselves. When firms with higher CSR disclosure quantity proxied by number of pages of CSR reports, they will have higher financial analyst coverage. Finally, firms with better social and environmental disclosure quality will attract more financial analysts following the firms.

Unique Contribution to Theory, Policy and Practice: This paper is the first examination of the impact of CSR disclosure on financial analyst behavior, to my knowledge. Unlike Dhaliwal et al. (2012), my research is to investigate the impact of CSR disclosures on financial analyst following. The results on this paper can help regulators to decide whether mandate firms issue stand-alone CSR reports or audit their

CSR reports to help financial analysts using those reports. What is more, the results shows better disclosure index on social and environment in CSR reports will attract more financial analysts following provide more accuracy of their forecasts. So, regulators can decide whether to mandate firms to disclose more social and environmental issues to financial analysts and investors.

Keywords: Corporate Social Responsibility, Financial Analysts, Disclosure Quality

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Introduction

Furthermore, likewise financial analysts in their earnings forecasting formulation process are highly covering for firms seeking professional opinions from auditors or hiring other independent professional service providers assurance increasing their credibility and reliability on their sustainability reports and they are also increasingly coverage for richer information providers, due to those reports can provide certain non-financial and financial information helping financial analysts to examine the corporate current profitability and predict corporate future earnings and those social and environmental activities can actually affect corporate current and future financial performance, so that financial analysts are more using corporate social and environment information during their forecasting process. To my knowledge, this empirical study yields the first evidence on this causality. Later provides the results of robustness tests in this paper performed whether all dependent, independent and control variables are best fitted in ordinary least squared regression models mainly adopted in this study, including the tests of autocorrelation, potential omitted correlated problems, normality of residuals, outliers, collinearity, and heteroscedasticity. In robustness, all variables are roughly suited in ordinary least square regression models, some of which model specifications are, however, subject to the heteroscedasticity problem, thereby this study will also, for remediation, adopt the generalized method of moments (GMM) to verify the validation of the previous regression results done in the last section.

Background

This paper investigates corporate sustainability (CSR) and the influence of CSR disclosure decision, increased disclosure and disclosure quality on financial analysts' coverage in different countries. Analysts' behaviour is examined as they may be considered to be sophisticated users of company information, and, unlike market expectations, their expectations are directly observable. Overall, here emphasis on CSR information quality is consistent with much prior work on non-financial disclosures (Gibbins *et al.*, 1990; Lang and Lundholm, 1993, 1996; Welker, 1995; Botosan, 1997; Healy *et al.*, 1999; Association for Investment Management and Research, 2000). Further, this paper will look at which disclosures within CSR reports appear to be useful for financial analysts in forecasting process in different countries. Corporate social responsibility has been discussed for a long time in the management, accounting and finance fields. They more focus on the influence

of CSR disclosure on firm financial performance. Much of the document that firms with better CSR performance such as employee relations, employee right protection, product quality and environment protection can boost revenues, reduce potential costs and increase firm future earnings (Akerlof, 1982; Yellen, 1984; Shapiro and Stiglitz, 1984; Margolis, Elfenbein, and Walsh, 2007; Orlitzky, 2008; van Beurden and Gossling, 2008; Carroll and Shabana, 2010; Wood, 2010; Grappi, Romani and Bagozzi, 2013; Sweetin et al, 2013). Furthermore, stakeholder theory, social-political theory, interest group theory, Legitimacy theory, and its framework also support the CSR activities are positively associated with firm financial performance and firms prefer to disclose CSR information to different stakeholders. Due to the influence on performance, analysts are likely to consider CSR disclosures supplemented with other accounting information for their forecasting as do other non-financial disclosures, thereby influencing on analysts following (Bouwman, Frishkoff and Frishkoff, 1995; Hopkins, Houston, and Peters, 2000; Jegadeesh and Livnat, 2006; Weiss, 2010).

In accounting and finance, CSR is also a long debating research area as the majority of previous researches examine social/ environmental disclosures alone even though several papers investigate the determinants of CSR disclosures and many have been published in management studies that examine the relationship between CSP and CFP only. In the past, researchers in accounting and finance have been restricted by the limited sample of firms issuing corporate social responsibility reports (and difficult to collect data by hands). Therefore, they are difficult to carry out empirical studies and instead most of them conduct business case analysis that creates result interference problem because most of the business case research are very limited with small sample size from several companies to a hundred¹, that may only reflect the condition for a specific industry but not all and small sample size may be not predicted to the population. In recent years, more and more firms have issued CSR reports and more non-profit organizations have collected them for users and researchers like Corporate Register² (<http://www.corporateregister.com>), Social Fund, GRI website and CSR-NEWS (<http://csr-news.net>). Therefore, *The Accounting Review* collaborated with Harvard Business School to host a CSR conference in 2012. My paper will look at this area in details. However, hundred of prior studies have not investigated how CSR disclosures affect the analysts behaviour in different countries and those haven't provided any evidence on this.

Study Motivations

Corporate social responsibility (also called as corporate conscience, corporate citizenship, social performance, or sustainable responsibility) is a form of corporate self-regulation related to social conscience that is normally integrated into a business strategies, decisions and operation.

CSR is a business process with an aim to embrace responsibility for the firms' actions on society and encourage firms a positive impact on the environment, consumers, employees, communities through its different CSR activities. "corporate social responsibility" become popular in the 1960s in different fields, including

¹ More detail CSR literature review can refer to section 2.

²It is an organization to collect CSR related information and resources, including the world's largest online directory of CSR and Sustainability Reports, the ReportingPartners CSR.

management, social science and so on. CSR activities including environmental protection: the firms introduce procedures for recycling, waste management, water discharge management, renewable energy utilization, establishing sustainable supply chains, paper-less operation, etc. Community supporting: firms should raise fund for local charities, support community volunteerism, sponsoring community events, etc. some argue that some corporations do CSR programs partially for the commercial benefit due to they enjoy it from improving their reputation with the public, with customers, with the employees or with government. For instance, Shell has well-imposed and publicized CSR policies to public but it has in the 2004 a scandal concerning its misreporting of oil reserves to adversely impact its reputation, in turn influencing corporate financial performance. In an example, Magellan Metals (Western Australia) was responsible for lead contamination that kills thousands of birds in the related area and that corporation was cease business immediately by force, resulting in financial disasters. Another company, Odwalla (San Francisco), experienced an environmental crisis resulting in sales dropping 90%, due to some cases of materials spread through apple juice. With prior studies' findings and many real cases in different industries, it supports CSR issues and its performance are likely to influence corporate financial performance, thereby the fact that it motives me to investigate how CSR reports influence whether financial analysts following a firm in various countries and in different periods.

Expected Contribution

The objective of my paper is to determine how decision of corporate sustainability disclosures and CSR disclosure quality influence on analyst behavior. The prior literature examines whether the CSR performance (activities and disclosures) can affect cost of financing and firm value (Roman et al., 1999; Orlitzky et al., 2003; Goss and Roberts, 2009; Dhaliwal et al., 2011). The prior work also examines any provide ex post evidence whether firms with better CSR performance have less earnings management (Kim et al, 2012) and reduce analysts forecast errors (Dhaliwal et al., 2012). These papers provide additional evidence on disclosure literature (e.g. Ali, Klasa, & Yeung, 2005; Chang, Khanna, and Palepu, 2000; Hope, 2003b; Lang and Lundholm, 1996; Lang, Lins, and Miller, 2003) because this paper justifies the relation between non-financial disclosures decision (using CSR disclosures) and analyst coverage; and the relation between disclosure quality (using CSR disclosure quality) and those behaviour supported from international evidence. It can see whether CSR disclosures are different from other non-financial information affecting analyst behaviour.

This more comprehensively examines whether the CSR decision and quality influence on analyst following, unlike other country-wide comparative studies as discussed before, they more focus on how differ CSR activities in different countries such as charitable donation, number of CSR issued reports, community involvement/ investment, CSR policies and etc, whereas this study is examining one of CSP measures, namely disclosure quality captured by self-developed research instrument. More specially, they have not investigated the economic consequences of CSP- disclosure on analyst behaviour but this study will try to do so. This paper comprehensively investigate the impact of CSR decision and quality on financial analysts through self-developed research measurement instrument analysing report content in details based on prior studies and GRI framework and migrate the above problems to provide more reliable evidence. Further, they have not examined which CSR disclosed items are useful for analysts but this paper will look at this in details.

Besides, many prior studies are focusing on the effect of CSR on financial performance (e.g. [Posnikoff, 1997](#); [Preston and O'Bannon, 1997](#); [Russo and Fouts, 1997](#); [Sharma and Verdenburg, 1998](#); [Teoh, Welch, and Wazzan, 1999](#); [Verschoor, 1998](#); [Johnson and Greening, 1999](#)) and few articles engage studying the institutional background (namely and country) and settle this biased problem.

For the social impact perspective, this paper can help regulators to consider whether mandatorily govern listed firms to disclosure CSR information to public and whether further require those firms to assure or audit their CSR report so as to provide more credible information to public because such disclosure can affect analysts, investors and other stakeholders' decision making. For economic impact perspective, this paper can provide additional evidence to regulators, standard-setters and investors on the stock market relevance of corporate social and environmental disclosure. It can also help regulators to consider whether it needs to issue accounting standards to compulsorily govern firms on presentation of such CSR information because if CSR disclosures are commonly used by analysts and other stakeholders, they likely prefer to have standardized contents and formats in the report for analysis. It can also encourage non-profit organization to enhance their monitoring roles toward those companies to perform better corporate social and environmental issues that not only influence the society as a whole but also shareholders and financial analysts' decision making because CSR initiatives not only influence the corporate reputation in the community but also affect customers, employees and suppliers' perception with companies' future earnings and risks. This paper, therefore, can partially answer why some companies can financially perform better than others and enjoy higher corporate reputation in community; in overall why social responsible companies can perform better than their counterparts. This may be resulted from country and time factors. Furthermore, this paper can also contribute to analyst literature how analysts incorporate non-financial information such as CSR information differently in different countries because this study comprehensively examines the effect of non-financial information on analysts' coverage and earning predication.

Regarding methodology, this study investigates the CSR disclosure quality rather than other CSP measures such as KLD, Fortune Most admired, charitable donations, disinvestment in CSR and so on when compared with [Orlitzky et al. \(2003\)](#), [Goss and Roberts \(2009\)](#). Measuring CSP using disclosures can comprehensively assess corporate social performance, instead of only one measure of CSR such as charitable donation, disinvestment in CSR, Fortune Most admired, entering CSR share indices that only evaluate one side of corporate CSR activities. Unlike [Dhaliwal et al. \(2011\)](#), [Kim et al. \(2012\)](#) who measure CSR reputation using KLD's rating, third party audit that include 5 dimensions, namely employee relations, diversity, local communities, environment, and product safety/quality, this study uses self-developed CSR research instrument to capture the wider corporate social performance in the report that includes 89 items in various CSR dimensions such as pollution control, pollution, environmental Strategies, Integrity and ethical policies, communities, public sector issues, corporate governance, employee, suppliers, customers, product issues and other dimensions. Besides, Unlike other studies, [Aerts, Cormier and Magnan \(2008\)](#) that only measure one

side of CSR activity, namely corporate communication and environment aspects but ignores other corporate social performance including community, employee relations, product quality, suppliers' CSR and corporate CSR policies, this study in turn develops its own CSR disclosure measure to cover all of these social and environmental performance.

Regarding sample size of content analysis (handcollection data) in data collection, compared with that in other studies such as [Freedman and Stagliano \(1991\)](#) using 27 firm-year, [Fiori et al. using \(2007\)](#) 25 firm-year, [Kapoor & Sandhu \(2010\)](#) using 93 firm-year, [Uadiale & Fagbemi \(2012\)](#) using 40 firm-year, [Weshah et al \(2012\)](#) using 13 firm-year observations, [Berman, Wicks, Kotha and Jones \(1999\)](#) using 81 firm-year, and other studies, all of them use very few sample companies in their studies but this study will use over three hundred firm-year observations for content analysis and over 2000 firm-year observations around the world to measure their CSP disclosures and its impact on financial analysts and even some regression models use more than 2000 firm-year observations to analyse the relation between corporate sustainability disclosure decision, quality and quantity on different financial analyst properties and behaviour. For the dependent variables, this study will differ from other CSR studies. Most of prior studies investigate CSP – CFP relations but this study examines the impact of CSR on intermediate of the security markets rather than the impact on corporate accounting-based financial performance or market-based financial performance.

Speaking of control variables that are used for reducing omitted correlated problems, many prior studies are subject to this problem creating invalidity of results because most of prior studies only commonly use size, industry, R&D, leverage, earnings, beta and corporate assets for control variables but it still ignores other control factors, thus this will use more than 10 control variables in various regression models to capture other institutional factors (later section will explain more details on this aspect). Some prior papers related to corporate social responsibility analysis use less than 5 control variables (e.g. [Shank, 2005](#); [Van de Velde, Vermeir, & Corten, 2005](#); [Berman, Wicks, Kotha, Jones, 1999](#); [Epstein and Wisner, 2001](#)), it makes their results in doubt, whereas, this article uses up more than 10 control variables to reduce the potential omitted correlated problem in the regression models.

This study can also encourage future research to investigate whether and how managers opportunistically disclose specific information in CSR report to influence investors or other stakeholders, as do other financial and non financial disclosures in annual reports. Finally, it can also encourage future research to develop a better model to find the comprehensive determinants of CSR disclosures, its quality and quantity.

Research Philosophy and Methodology

This study will conduct empirical analysis and employ statistical analysis to test different research hypotheses that are constructed and explained in accordance with accounting, economic and management theoretical frameworks such as stakeholder theory, stakeholder-agency theory, interest group theory, Legitature theory and etc, and findings established from the relevant literature. Stakeholder theory of CSR is used as an explanatory theory in the context to describe why companies react with stakeholders' demands. Stakeholder-

agency theory is also used to explain why companies have to satisfy stakeholders' concern to reduce their utility loss arising from poor CSR initiatives. Otherwise, companies with poor corporate social performance may induce stakeholders to impose more complexity structures so as to reduce their utility losses by enacting laws and regulations, being monitored by watchdogs and so on that likely adverse influence their financial performance. Legitature theory is used as an explanatory theory in the context to explain companies have to respond stakeholders as a whole so as to be granted their operation in community. Other related theories support why companies disclose CSR information that is also the main concern of this study, to public. The sample of this study is drawn from the Financial Times top global 500 companies in the world from the testing period of 2008 to 2012. Firms without Datastream, Worldscope, CRSP, Compustat, IBES data in databases and necessary CSR data in the CSR reports are excluded from the analysis.

Like other studies, univariate analyses are conducted and performed to report the descriptive statistics for the variables used in the multivariate analysis. Two-tailed t-test and p-value with 90%, 95% and 99% confident intervals would be adopted in this study. What is more, this study will also adopt the One-way ANOVA to compare the mean difference of number of financial analysts between both companies with release of standalone CSR reports and without standalone CSR reports, between both firms with assurance of their CSR reports and firms without assurance of their CSR reports, both firms with issuing more number of pages of corporate social responsibility reports and firms with issuing less number of pages of corporate social responsibility reports, both firms with high social disclosure score of corporate social responsibility reports and firms with low social disclosure score of corporate social responsibility reports, and both firms with high environmental disclosure score of corporate social responsibility reports and firms with low environmental disclosure score of CSR reports. R-square and Chi-square test to verify the variety of different regression models. An Ordinary Least square regression is also used to empirically test the hypotheses of this study. The dependent variables are used for capturing different analyst behaviour. There are various independent variables including whether companies decide to issue standalone report or not, what CSR items disclosed in those reports and whether CSR assurance by third party or not. Control variables adopted in this study will include company characteristics (e.g. size, leverage, profitability, listing status, forecast horizons, analyst characteristics and so on). SPSS, R & E-views econometric and statistic software packages are used to progress the multivariate ordinary least regression analysis and generalized method of moment analysis with some robustness. Finally, data on corporate social responsibility disclosures are needed to hand collect from standalone reports of sampling companies.

Background on Corporate Social Responsibility

Since most people are able to feel emotions, they can comprehend what it means to be accountable. People frequently turn to their conscience for direction when faced with difficult moral decisions. These people are likely to feel noticeable emotional discomfort when they witness their own careless behavior because their conscience acts as a guide for moral behavior. People are equally likely to experience unease when they witness others, including businesses, acting irresponsibly. "The state or fact of being responsible, answerable, or accountable for something within one's power, control, or management" is how the World Dictionary defines responsibility. According to this definition, responsibility has to do with a person's innate capacity to address or take accountability for their own actions and behavior. The idea that people are held accountable by others for things they are in charge of is also implied in this definition. These can include responsibilities, duties, and the ability to discriminate between right and wrong. Companies are accountable for their actions,

just like people are. According to **Davis (1967)**, businesses have two social obligations to uphold. First, a company's duty to advance the general economic well-being is known as socio-economic responsibility. The company's obligation to use business practices that uphold or advance fundamental human values is known as socio-human responsibility. Although he acknowledged that businesses have a role to play in advancing social and economic well-being, he also maintained that businesses are not the only ones doing so. **Davis (1967)**. Wood put forth the Principle of Public Responsibility in connection with this. According to this principle, business and society are interdependent systems since businesses are accountable for the consequences of their actions on society. Because they work in a shared environment, businesses should be socially responsible. Businesses should conduct their operations in a socially responsible manner since they share an environment with other societal entities. In order to achieve this, businesses should follow general principles that advance the advancement of society at large in addition to laws and regulations.

Early discussions of corporate social responsibility (CSR) in the 1990s focused on the relative benefits of CSR initiatives, CSR performance, and CSR-related regulations that affect an organization's earnings, reputation, cost of capital, and stock return. Fundamental questions about the responsibilities and duties of businesses that participate in CSR initiatives were not fully addressed in these discussions. In this sense, accountability was not seen as a crucial component of running a business. Accepting responsibility, however, has long been a crucial prerequisite for people, organizations, and societies to promote friendly interaction. Even so, it is unclear why a particular entity—whether it be societal, corporate, or individual—engages in responsible behavior. The achievement of sustainability and financial success is one area of continuous research into this issue in relation to corporations. Here, a quick look at four broad (and increasingly inclusive) viewpoints on why organizations act responsibly is instructive. These are known as the rational, humanist, holistic, and spiritual perspectives, respectively, and each has its own history, logic, and vocabulary. The rational perspective's proponents contend that businesses act responsibly in order to accomplish goals that are regarded as high priorities. Increasing market share, market capitalization, financial growth, and shareholder value are a few of these objectives. Early in the 20th century, this viewpoint was developed (**Taylor, 1998**). The humanist viewpoint, in contrast to the rational one, holds that a person's responsible behavior is a natural byproduct of being human and does not stem from a desire for material gains. The humanists, who date back to the 1950s and 1980s, contend that businesses' main duties are related to the workplace, including employee motivation and self-actualization. The holistic perspective is predicated on the idea that people within corporations are essentially interconnected and dependent on one another. It was first brought up in connection with responsible corporate behavior in the late 1960s, but it gained more popularity in the 1980s and 1990s (**Freeman, 1984**). They both have an obligation to respect one another's rights as a result of their interdependence. Supporters of the holistic viewpoint contend that a company's leader has duties that go beyond maximizing profits for shareholders. Rather, a corporate leader should take actions that benefit all stakeholders in the organization, according to the holistic perspective. The holistic approach thus questions conventional conceptions of corporate responsibility and success. Many businesses have started to report more comprehensive performance metrics in accordance with this viewpoint. For instance, a lot of businesses have begun creating new reports with "triple-bottom-line reporting." In a similar vein, several businesses have embraced international reporting standards to display company information (e.g. **Global Reporting Initiative, 2007**). Lastly, the spiritual viewpoint asserts that our inclination to take on responsibility is rooted in our basic characteristics. Advocates of this viewpoint contend that people have an innate desire to discover their true spiritual selves and follow their destiny. Writings on leadership from the 1990s served as the inspiration for

this viewpoint. Regarding the spiritual viewpoint, Greenleaf (1998) maintained that a leader is more likely to act in ways that go beyond their own self-interest once they have grown in their own spiritual self-awareness.

Even though corporate social responsibility was first introduced decades ago, more people are becoming concerned about it in the twenty-first century. Beyond the company's immediate interests and what is required by law, corporate social responsibility (CSR) initiatives aim to advance social goods (McWilliams and Siegel, 2001). Beyond their duties and duty of care to shareholders, corporations have societal obligations (Doh and Guay, 2006). The concept of corporate social responsibility (CSR) holds businesses accountable to a variety of stakeholders, including communities, workers, suppliers, employees, the government, and environmentalists.

These days, businesses and academics from the fields of business, accounting, and finance are looking into these factors, practices, and their effects. CSR has been defined in a variety of ways over the last few decades. According to one study, there are 37 distinct ways to define corporate social responsibility (Dahlsrud, 2008). Nonetheless, a number of academics continue to criticize the absence of precise definitions of corporate social responsibility (CSR) (Bowman and Haire, 1975; Carroll, 1999; Frankental, P., 2001; Holmes, 1976; Van., 2003). The founder of the corporate social responsibility (CSR) movement, Bowen (1953), was the first to define CSR as the "social responsibilities of businessmen/businesswomen." He asserts that a businessman must make choices that are desirable for societal goals and values rather than just those that benefit the company internally. Frederick contends that companies' resources ought to be allocated for more general social objectives as opposed to just internal ones (Frederick, 1960). CSR is "business and society are interwoven rather than distinct entities," according to Wood (1991a,b). Businesses should have a moral obligation to contribute positively to the community, claim Brown and Dacin (1997). The definition of corporate social responsibility (CSR) is expanded by Maignan et al. (1999) and Sen and Bhattacharya (2001) to include a company's moral commitment to make a positive contribution to the community. According to Jones et al. (2009), social responsibilities include: (1) taking steps to prevent pollution and environmental degradation; (2) treating employees as valuable assets within the company; (3) increasing public involvement in corporate issues; (4) going above and beyond legal requirements; (5) implementing ethical policies within the company; and (6) making decisions that are sustainable. In a similar vein, Kotler and Lee (2005) define corporate social responsibility (CSR) as an organization's pledge to use its resources to advance societal well-being. According to Matten and Moon (2008), there should be no definition for corporate social responsibility (CSR) because it encompasses a wide range of related ideas and has evolved into various classifications as society's values have changed. In contrast to ethics, which is more internal to the company, CSR is mainly external. In addition to creating a positive work environment for staff, the community, and society at large, businesses must act morally and support economic growth in order to demonstrate socially responsible behavior (Watts and Holme, 1999). As a result, CSR is seen as multifaceted. Conversely, Armstrong (1977) characterizes social irresponsibility as when businesses make choices that solely benefit one party at the expense of other parties and, worse, the system as a whole. By classifying businesses' operations according to these various CSR types, classes, and kinds, it can employ an alternative method to identify distinct CSR categories. Carroll (1979; 1991) distinguishes four categories of business social responsibilities: philanthropic, legal, ethical, and economic.

Since they imply that businesses have social as well as legal and financial responsibilities, the aforementioned definitions have been effectively applied in academic research for more than 25 years (Carroll and Shabana,

2010). Even though many people still contend that these categories of social responsibilities are ambiguous, they can still shed light on corporate social responsibility (Enderle, 2010). Scholars from the US and Europe contributed to the independent development of the meaning of each CSR component in the 1980s and 1990s (e.g., Balderjahn, 1988 develops the meaning for sustainability). Eventually, environmental preservation and social responsibility are combined into one area known as corporate social responsibility (Schlegelmilch, 1994). In any case, the social activities and the social repercussions of corporate success are still reflected in the core of CSR. Furthermore, according to Skarmeas and Leonidou (2013), corporate social involvement is not limited to a small number of businesses but rather is a widespread and standard practice for many of them. CSR programs exist in almost all developed nations, and emerging nations are also doing some preliminary research and development.

CSR is an essential part of organizational practice, regardless of its advantages or disadvantages. It has an impact on external stakeholders' behaviors as well as every facet of internal corporate operations. The responses of organizational partners provide the clearest justification for the significance of CSR. For instance, consumers are increasingly looking for high-quality goods from reliable businesses in recent years. In a similar vein, suppliers want to work with trustworthy businesses. Workers favor organizations that provide respect from managers and favorable working conditions. Mutual funds that prioritize social responsibility seek to invest in businesses that have demonstrated strong social and environmental performance. Nonprofit organizations are eager to collaborate with businesses that tackle issues that are important to them. Lastly, the public has a tendency to pay attention to businesses that they believe are socially conscious of the communities in which they operate. In addition to maximizing profit and committing to the financial objectives of shareholders, companies can cultivate positive relationships with these stakeholder groups by meeting their diverse interests. Since it enables them to execute strategies that satisfy all corporate constituents, socially responsible behavior on the part of businesses has become increasingly important for their success. As a result, businesses that practice social responsibility are better prepared to thrive in a challenging, international business climate where they must manage competing stakeholder interests.

In order to understand CSR disclosures, the stakeholder theory is crucial (Deegan, 2002; Brammer and Pavelin, 2006; and Clarkson et al., 2008). According to Freeman's (1984) traditional definition, a stakeholder is "any group of individuals who can affect or are affected by the achievement of a firm's objectives." Owners, creditors, employees, suppliers, distributors, local communities, and customers are examples of stakeholders, according to Armstrong and Green (2013). According to Clarkson (1995), all stakeholders can be divided into primary and secondary stakeholders. Priority is given to primary stakeholders because the organization views their financial and non-financial support as essential. Shareholders, workers, clients, suppliers, lenders, governments, and communities are all included in this category. Secondary stakeholders do not have a transactional relationship with the organization and are not typically thought of as essential to its survival. The media, consumer advocates, and environmentalists are examples of this type. From the lowest to the highest priorities, Mitchell et al. (1997) divide stakeholders into eight groups according to their salience: non-stakeholder, dormant, discretionary, demanding, dangerous, dominant, dependent, and definitive. The term "stakeholder theory" was first used by Ansoff (1965), who is in many ways a true forerunner of Freeman (1984). A firm's goal is to balance the conflicts among its stakeholders, according to Freeman's extension of the theory. By evaluating the relationships between businesses and stakeholders according to exchange transactions, power dependencies, legitimacy claims, or other claims, stakeholder theory aims to methodically address the question of which stakeholders do and do not deserve or require management attention (Mitchell

et al., 1997). Additionally, **Carroll and Shabana (2010)** contend that "businesses are not looking for anything specific in return, and that social responsibility is primarily driven by external, socially conscious motivations." Stakeholders have an impact on the quality of CSR disclosures and firm CSR activities, which can also be explained by the stakeholder theory.

Freeman (1983) created this theory of organizational management, which is a small component of business ethics, to address the pressures that organizations face from both the inside and the outside. Different stakeholders and their interests in organizations are identified by **Freeman (1983)**. According to the conventional wisdom, an organization's shareholders are its true owners, and they only have a fiduciary and duty of care to look out for their interests. According to stakeholder theory, the company and its policies can be influenced by a variety of other stakeholders, including the government, creditors, suppliers, customers, competitors, employees, trade unions, labor unions, political groups, and communities. However, there is much debate regarding the characteristics of stakeholders (**Miles, 2012**). Numerous scholars have refined and streamlined the theory since **Freeman (1983)** first proposed it (e.g. **Donaldson and Preston, 1995; Mitchell et al, 1997**). It serves as a framework for CSR. The environment, equal employment opportunities, community, product safety, energy conservation, and social responsibility disclosures are just a few of the topics covered by corporate social responsibility (CSR) initiatives (**Cowen et al., 1987**). However, a key component of stakeholder theory is its effort to pinpoint the various groups and social concerns that exist within a community and that businesses may be obligated to address. Due to the lack of a theoretical framework for the study of CSR activities, **Ullmann (1985)** created a contingency framework based on **Freeman's (1983)** stakeholder theory. The connection between corporate social disclosures and the financial effects on business performance can be explained by **Ullmann's (1985)** theoretical framework. Additionally, it can be used to forecast the volume of CSR disclosures and activities. This framework's development is predicated on the stakeholder theory, which was created by **Freeman (1983)**.

A three-dimensional model explaining the connection between financial performance, social performance, and corporate social disclosure is documented by **Ullmann (1985)**. Businesses can react to stakeholder demands in the first dimension. Investors, financial analysts, creditors, customers, suppliers, and regulators are examples of stakeholders who can have an impact on management's CSR disclosures and actions. According to **Ullmann (1985)**, the firms' CSR performance and disclosures are positively correlated with the power of stakeholders and their expectations regarding CSR. The decision makers' internal drive to accommodate the demands of external stakeholders is the second dimension. The corporate stance with stakeholders can be actively or passively influenced by management. It is reasonable to assume that more CSR disclosures and activities will result from management's active responses. The third dimension is financial performance, both past and present; the degree of CSR activities and disclosures can be influenced by firm capacity. The ability of this stakeholder theory to explain a particular CSR activity—corporate social disclosures—is empirically tested by **Roberts (1992)**. According to his theory, companies that perform better will have more money to devote to their CSR initiatives, which will increase the likelihood that they will make these disclosures.

This is my paper's primary goal. This section will therefore concentrate more on this section. The CSR framework is based on two primary lines of existing research. The impact of corporate social responsibility initiatives' financial ramifications on business performance is the subject of one research avenue. The results show a positive trend. As an example, consider **Chen and Metcalf (1980), Anderson and Frankle (1980),**

Akerlof (1982), Shane and Spicer (1983), Cochran and Wood (1984), Shapiro and Stiglitz (1984), Yellen (1984), Margolis, Elfenbein, and Walsh (2007), Orlitzky (2008), van Beurden and Gossling (2008), Carroll and Shabana (2010), Wood (2010), Gappi, Romani, and Bagozzi (2013), and Sweetin et al (2013). According to Mahapatra (1984), social responsibility initiatives and disclosures can also lower systemic risks. The factors that influence CSR disclosures and activities are the subject of another research avenue. According to Mills and Gardner (1984), a company is more inclined to reveal its social responsibility expenses in a given year if it has a strong financial year. Additional research thoroughly investigates the connection between CSR disclosures and firm attributes (e.g., firm size, industry, current profitability, past market and book performance, presence of CSR committees, and reputation). Their findings indicate that the extent of CSR disclosures can be influenced by industry classification, firm size, and past performance (Cochran and Wood, 1984; McGuire et al., 1988).

Societies that are made up of and impacted by historical and cultural factors are where organizations exist and function. For reasons that fall into one of three main categories—interest-based, rights-based, or duty-based accountabilities—organizations must respond to demands from diverse stakeholders. The foundation of interest-based demands for corporate accountability is the inherent investment that stakeholders have in organizations (e.g., organizations pay employees). The idea that stakeholders take into account organizational resource distribution, as well as corporate opportunities and output, is the foundation of rights-based demands of corporate accountability. The belief among stakeholders that companies must take on responsibilities that go beyond financial performance (i.e., profitability, efficiency, and liquidity) is linked to duty-based demands of corporate responsibility. Furthermore, it is likely that different stakeholders will have different organizational interests, according to stakeholder theory. Accordingly, stakeholder theorists contend that maintaining organizational legitimacy and success requires striking a balance between the interests of the various stakeholders (Shankman, 1999).

Because corporate stakeholders have the agency power to influence corporate actions, proponents of stakeholder theory (Freeman, 1984; Clarkson, 1995; Donaldson and Preston, 1995; Mitchell et al., 1997) have argued that there is a positive correlation between CSR and corporate financial performance (CFP). The scandals involving Enron, WorldCom, and other multinational corporations, for example, have illustrated the dangers of concentrating solely on an organization's financial obligation to shareholders.

Freeman's (1983) stakeholder theory served as the foundation for Ullmann's (1985) contingency framework. The purpose of Ullmann's (1985) theoretical framework is to explain how corporate social responsibility and business financial performance are related. According to him, the fact that only successful businesses have the resources to participate in CSR-related activities may be the reason for the positive correlation between CSR and firm performance. On the other hand, the favorable relationship might be a sign that management of the company can concurrently attend to the demands and needs of different external stakeholders. Numerous theories have also been put forth by other researchers in this field to explain the connection between corporate social responsibility (CSR) and a company's financial performance (e.g. Aupperle et al., 1985; Wartick and Cochran, 1985; Wood 1991a, 1991b; Pava and Krausz, 1996; Wood and Jones, 1995; Husted, 2000; McWilliams and Siegel, 2001). The relationship between corporate financial performance, stakeholder reactions, CSR performance, and CSR actions is illustrated in Appendix A. Positive and negative stakeholder reactions to company CSR initiatives, such as increased customer purchases, consumer protests, employee resistance or loyalty, and government regulations responding to such activities that can impact corporate

profits, are typical ways that CSR affects CFP. The impact of business operations on society's social and environmental fabric, which in turn affects business financial performance, is another way that CSR influences CFP. Companies can improve employee satisfaction and product safety by implementing CSR strategies like employee training or incentive enhancement. This improves the company's reputation and encourages more customers to buy its products, which boosts sales and profits. Businesses can upgrade their corporate technology to lower emissions, increase product safety, and decrease fines and penalties for product dispenses. This will lower costs, boost consumer spending, improve community relations, and raise CSR ratings.

Corporate Social Responsibility Performance and Financial Performance

Out of the 100 largest economies in the world (as determined by GDP), 51 are US corporations and 49 are nation-states, according to data from the Office of Economic Co-operation and Development. This result demonstrates how multinational corporations have largely replaced nation-states as the dominant force in the world economy. Because of their enormous economic power, corporations have been held accountable for a great deal of social responsibility.

It goes without saying that participating in CSR initiatives involves both immediate and long-term financial outlays. These expenses frequently include the purchase of new, eco-friendly machinery, adjustments to organizational structures, or the introduction of stricter quality control measures. Businesses benefit from their societal legitimacy even though they are forced to pay costs associated with corporate social responsibility. Although many of these advantages are non-monetary (such as enhanced corporate social reputation), CSR initiatives can also yield numerous financial gains. For instance, customers are more likely to view businesses that practice social responsibility favorably. These customers are therefore less likely to be attracted to such businesses.

Furthermore, bad things don't happen to socially conscious businesses. For instance, a business that has a reputation for upholding its social obligations might be thought to enforce stringent guidelines for product quality and environmental preservation. They are therefore thought to have a lower likelihood of recalling faulty goods or paying fines for excessive pollution. Companies can use a method that measures additional benefits from advertising campaigns after implementing certain SR activities or actions, even though it is still challenging to accurately measure the benefits derived from a company's improved reputation arising from improvement of their social responsibilities.

Socially conscious businesses are likely to experience steady earnings growth and low business risk, as demonstrated by the aforementioned concerns. Certain CSR initiatives, like redesigning or repackaging products to reduce material waste and streamlining delivery truck routes, can significantly lower operating costs.

The relationship between a company's financial performance and its socially responsible behavior is determined and measured using empirical methods. One area of study examines how corporate social responsibility initiatives affect the economy, particularly how they affect a company's performance now and in the future. This is typically measured using a variety of short- and long-term metrics, to mention a few. Prior research on corporate profitability typically used sales-profit margin, net income, and earnings per share; prior research on corporate growth likely used return on sales ratio, return on equity, and earnings per share growth over the next two, three, and five years; prior research on corporate asset utilization likely used return

on investments and asset turnover; and previous research on corporate liquidity, including the acid test, current ratio, and payout ratio, among others, supporting the idea that CSR actions have a negative correlation with business risk and strategic corporate decisions and a positive correlation with both short- and long-term accounting performance (Orlitzky and Benjamin, 2001; Orlitzky, Schmidt and Rynes, 2003; McWilliams, Siegel, and Wright, 2006). Numerous previous studies have used various measures of corporate financial performance, as Table 4.1 demonstrates. Table 4.2 illustrates the likely effects of corporate social responsibility on market-based financial performance and corporate accounting in various dynamics. It can provide supporting empirical evidence for this research assumption by summarizing the results of CSP-CFP relations over the past forty years. Scholars have steadily created a thorough definition of corporate social performance (CSR), but even with this definition, there are still many different ways to measure CSP. Previous research has frequently used 11 different corporate practice domains (environment, community investment, omnibus/global, services/products, human resources, human rights, CSR disclosures, organizational programs, business practice) and 27 different data sources (such as KLD, CSP survey, charity donation, policies, Fortune most admired, CEP (environmental practices), 10-K disclosures, annual report disclosure, Moskowitz selection, TRI/IRRC, and so on) to evaluate social performance. Because they contend that multiple approaches can accurately and completely reflect corporate social practices and performance, some of them used a variety of methods and metrics to evaluate corporate social performance. The sample types used in earlier studies, however, were fairly similar and included the Fortune 500, Standard & Poor's 500, Fortune Most Admired, Fortune 1250, Business Week 1000, Forbes, CEP, Moskowitz, and a few particular industries. Table 4.2 lists 40 previous studies conducted over the past ten years that use a variety of approaches to examine how different CSR measures impact corporate financial performance in terms of different accounting and market-based measures. According to a review of previous research, the majority of these studies use a third-party audit approach to measure CSR performance. Examples of these include the 1992 Toxics Release Inventory, the Fortune Corporate Reputation Survey, the FRDC's rating, the KLD ratings (community, employees, environment, products, women, minorities, military nuclear, South Africa), The Fortune reputation database, Investor Responsibility Research Center's Corporate Environmental Profile, EPA's Toxic Release Inventory (TRI) data, Vigeo CSR score, Ethical Investment Research Service (EIRIS) data, Canadian Social Investment database rating, and other databases have been removed by Brown & Perry. The amount of charitable donations is then used to gauge CSR investment and involvement, and various research instruments with different dimensions (such as community, environment management, employee relations, etc.) are used to gauge CSR disclosure in annual reports. Event studies are used to gauge accounting-based and market-based financial performance (e.g., divestment from South Africa, Fortune most admired, admired in other CSR indices, etc.). They typically use ROE, ROA, ROS, earnings, and expenses as indicators of CSR accounting-based performance, and abnormal stock returns and share price as indicators of CSR market-based performance. Their research sample sizes range from 7 to 2250 firm-years. Moreover, they frequently employ the following control variables in their studies: size, beta, price-to-book, momentum, industry, leverage, R&D, debt to equity ratio, total assets, and EPS. Their findings generally indicate that corporate financial performance is positively connected with environmental compliance, employee relations, product safety, and the environment across a range of metrics. Additionally, it reveals that CSR disclosure has the strongest positive correlation with a variety of market-based and accounting-based corporate financial performance metrics out of all CSP measures. In accordance with the findings of the previous study, this one will use corporate social responsibility (CSR) disclosures from businesses as a gauge of their corporate social performance. It will then look at how the number of financial analysts is affected by the choice, quality, and quantity of disclosures.

More than dozens of CSR-CSP studies have been conducted in the 1980s and 1990s, including four significant influencing studies published in the 1990s (Frooman, 1997; Griffin and Mahon, 1997; Preston and O' Bannon, 1997; Waddock and Graves, 1997) that have thoroughly examined this relationship. Giffin and Mahon (1997), for example, used the vote counting approach to review previous studies of the relationship between CSR and financial performance. They categorize 62 research outcomes from previous literature to identify 33 research outcomes that had a positive CSR-CFP relationship, 20 research outcomes that had a negative relationship, and 9 research outcomes that had an inconclusive relationship. Both relationships are reviewed in greater detail by Margolis and Walsh (2002). The majority of the 122 studies that empirically investigated the relationship between CFP and CSR and were published between 1971 and 2001 were positive, according to Margolis and Walsh (2002). Between 1971 and 2000, the number of studies demonstrating a positive relationship between CSP and CFP increased (Margolis and Walsh, 2003). Positive relationships appear to outweigh other CSR-CFP relationships. In fact, more than 90% of the previous research shows that corporate social responsibility (CSR) and present and future financial performance are positively correlated. Orlitzky et al. (2003) contend that the methodology used by Giffin and Mahon (1997) does not accurately depict the positive correlation between financial performance and corporate social responsibility. A subsequent meta-analysis of fifty-two previous studies confirms that CSP and CFP are positively correlated. Giffin and Mahon understated the positive relationship, according to a large population of previous quantitative studies. It should be noted that previous researchers primarily used the stock market's response to possible corporate social and environmental violations (such as product recalls) to find the majority of negative relationships. In actuality, there is still a positive correlation between poor corporate financial performance and poor CSR performance, and vice versa.

Corporate Social Responsibility and Market Reactions

Domestic and international markets frequently respond to corporate social responsibility (CSR) disclosures. Bushman and Smith's (2003) research showed that when specific kinds of information are made public (such as details about R&D projects, product quality, and employee backgrounds), markets use the information to evaluate how reliable a company's disclosures are and modify assessments of the company's profitability. For this reason, reporting environmental issues is crucial (Blacconiere and Patten, 1994). Corporate disclosures about adherence to environmental preservation may be partially harmful to a firm's funding costs, as demonstrated by Richardson and Welker (2001). Higher levels of voluntary environmental disclosure and general corporate social responsibility (CSR) disclosure are linked to lower costs of equity capital and higher firm values in the United States, according to two recent studies (Plumlee et al. 2008; Dhaliwal et al. 2011). Accordingly, a significant body of empirical research has demonstrated that investors use environmental preservation-related disclosed information when making capital market decisions (Blacconiere and Patten, 1994; Blacconiere and Northcut, 1997; Graham et al., 2000; Richardson and Welker, 2001). In many nations, there is also an increase in stakeholder interest in environmental issues (Bebbington et al., 2000; Cormier and Magnan, 2003). According to some researchers, market-based performance is impacted by environmental disclosures (Blacconiere and Patten, 1994).

Higher CSR activity improves a company's marketing, human resources, and other areas while also increasing financial performance. According to some academics, a global financial crisis makes corporate social responsibility even more crucial (Putrevu et al., 2013). Additionally, more recent scandals (Enron and WorldCom) have caused corporations to shift their focus from maximizing shareholder wealth to a border corporate strategy. As a result, more businesses are committing to CSR initiatives (Pinkston and Carroll, 1994).

To increase employees' awareness and understanding of CSR issues, many large corporations (like Cisco) implement various CSR programs (Murray and Vogel, 1997; Drumwright and Murphy, 2001; Joyner and Payne, 2002; Bhattacharya and Sen, 2004). As a result, one of the CSR activities, CSR disclosures, is becoming more common (Ramanathan, 1976; Ball et al., 2000a; Kamp-Roelands, 2002). For example, there were more than 1,000 independent CSR reports in 2007 compared to less than 100 in the mid-1990s (Dhaliwal et al., 2012). Furthermore, long-term survival and stockholder wealth maximization depend on the company's reputation and stakeholders' well-being. The wealth of shareholders and stakeholders should be connected since shareholders are only a party to the overall surplus of stakeholders. Because CSR can strengthen ties between the company and its stakeholders and improve its reputation among consumers, employees, regulators, suppliers, and the media, mainstream resource-based view scholars argue that there is a positive relationship between CSR and corporate financial performance (Haley, 1991; Waddock and Graves, 1997; Berman et al., 1999; Orlitzky et al., 2003; Brammer and Pavalin, 2006; Carmeli et al., 2007). Employees, customers, governments, and the media are among the stakeholders who typically react favorably to corporate social responsibility (CSR) initiatives in companies with positive stakeholder relations (Chen and Meindl, 1991; Henriques and Sadosky, 1999; Berman, Wicks, Kotha, and Jones, 1999). This, in turn, enhances the company's reputation and boosts economic performance (Agle et al., 1999; Roman et al., 1999; Margolis and Walsh, 2003; Tang, Hull and Rothenberg, 2012). For example, 127 and 52 studies, respectively, since the 1970s are summarized by Margolis and Walsh (2003) and Roman et al. (1999), who discover a generally positive correlation between these two performance measures. Additionally, a number of business literatures also find that CSR activities have an impact on risk and market-based performance (McWilliams, Siegel, and Wright, 2006; Orlitzky and Benjamin, 2001; Orlitzky, Schmidt, and Rynes, 2003). It follows that a large number of investors might favor funding socially conscious businesses. They want those companies to care more about society as a whole. Financial analysts probably take CSR initiatives into account when making forecasts, as investors respond to them.

Generally speaking, while several previous researchers have demonstrated a positive correlation between CSP and CFP, they have not demonstrated the nature of this relationship. However, this question has been thoroughly examined in more recent empirical treatments of the problem. First, it's critical to remember that CSR encompasses all activities pertaining to human rights, the environment, diversity, employee rights and relations, community development, and product quality control (Klein and Dawar, 2004). A lot of these CSR components have an impact on business profitability, which in turn has an impact on shareholder wealth. By tackling these problems, socially conscious businesses can set themselves apart from their rivals, enhancing their reputation and public image (Fombrun and Shanley, 1990), gaining the trust and goodwill of their clients, and fostering positive attitudes among their staff (Maignan et al., 1999; Rupp et al., 2006; Brammer et al., 2007; Valentine and Fleischman, 2008). Companies can improve their long-term financial performance (McWilliams and Siegel, 2000; Margolis and Walsh, 2001, Orlitzky and Benjamin, 2001; Orlitzky et al., 2003) and the price of their stock (Narver, 1971; Verrecchia, 1983; Freedman and Jaggi, 1992) by reducing the risk of employee or customer backlash. These claims have also been validated by some previous studies (see Rockness, Schlachter, and Rockness, 1986).

In the end, these results imply that stakeholder welfare and corporate reputation are crucial factors to take into account when trying to maximize shareholder wealth and guarantee long-term financial viability. Stakeholder benefits and shareholder financial wealth should be connected since shareholders are the only group impacted by corporate decisions. As a result, researchers who embrace the resource-based approach firmly contend that

there is a positive correlation between CSP and CFP (Haley, 1991; Waddock and Graves, 1997 ; Berman et al., 1999; Orlitzky et al., 2003 ; Brammer and Pavalin, 2006; Carmeli et al., 2007). Employees, clients, governments, and the media generally react favorably to a company's corporate social responsibility (CSR) initiatives when the company has strong corporate-stakeholder relationships (Chen and Meindl, 1991; Henriques and Sadorsky, 1999; Berman, Wicks, Kotha, and Jones, 1999). The company's reputation and future financial performance are subsequently impacted by this (Agle et al., 1999; Roman et al., 1999; Margolis and Walsh, 2003; Tang, Hull and Rothenberg, 2012). Therefore, in order to understand how CSR influences mediators and subsequently affects corporate accounting-based and market-based financial performance, this section examines the relationship between corporate social responsibility initiatives and corporate financial performance. It also determines the mediators between CSR activities and corporate financial performance.

Role of Financial Analysts

In reference to the function of financial analysts in capital markets, scholars Livnat and Zhang (2012) offer more recent evidence to support the two crucial roles that state financial analysts play in the capital market: they are information discoverers (Ivkovic and Jegadeesh, 2004; Ramnath et al., 2008; Chen et al., 2010) and information interpreters (Francis et al., 2002 and Frankel et al., 2006). Financial analysts' information-discovering role involves listening in on conference calls, speaking with corporate executives, and talking with business partners to obtain confidential information from the companies they follow. In order to forecast corporate future earnings and cash flow more accurately than counterparties, they would use such confidential information that is included in analyst forecasts. Financial analysts' job as information interpreters is to analyze and appraise publicly available corporate data (such as annual reports, social and environmental reports, corporate press releases, and public announcements) before incorporating it into their projections. Previous research has shown inconsistencies and even contradictions. According to Ivkovic and Jegadeesh (2004), markets respond more strongly to analyst revisions prior to earnings announcements than to those made after. This suggests that the information discovery role is better supported because the revisions made prior to earnings announcements most likely take into account analysts' acquisitions of confidential information from the companies. This conclusion depends on whether or not pre-earnings revisions accurately represent analysts' acquisition of confidential information. This approach, however, is awkward and barely distinguishes between the interpretative and discovery roles—both of which are crucial in analyst revisions—because other information may be made public prior to earnings announcements. A more comprehensive data set is offered by Livnat and Zhang (2012), who concentrate on a wide variety of corporate disclosures from various disclosure vehicles. They discover that analysts' interpretive skills, which are based on a proxy of market reactions to forecast revisions released immediately after corporate information, are valued by investors 30% more than their capacity to unearth confidential information. Financial analysts are therefore crucial to the capital markets because they can obtain confidential information from companies they follow by interviewing top management, participating in conference calls, speaking with business partners, and interpreting public information from companies. This increases the efficiency of information. Furthermore, since many investors are depending more on financial analysts' predictions and suggestions when making investment decisions, they play a crucial role in adjusting market expectations. As a result, analyst consensus forecasts are used in many accounting and finance studies as a stand-in for market expectations. Furthermore, new research indicates that companies are very concerned about meeting market expectations, which implies that managers are also interested in the forecasts and recommendations of analysts (Bartov et al., 2002; Lopez and Rees, 2002). According to Kasznik and Lev (1995), Bradshaw and Sloan (2002), Matsumoto (2002), Abarbanella

and Lehavy (2003), Dechow et al. (2003), Doyle et al. (2003), Bhattacharya et al. (2003), Bowen et al. (2005), Burgstahler and Eames (2006), Roychowdhury (2006), Black and Christensen (2009), Gunny (2010), Doyle, Jennings and Soliman (2013).

Factors affect Financial Analysts follow a company?

Theoretical literatures about information supply and demand (e.g., Grossman, 1978; Grossman and Stiglitz, 1980, Hellwig, 1980; Diamond and Verrecchia, 1981; Verrecchia, 1982; Admati, 1985; Admati and Pfleiderer, 1986, and Bhushan, 1989a) are actually related to the problem of analyst following. The number of analysts who follow a company is determined by the level of demand for the company's financial analyst services, or it can be seen as the equilibrium between the total supply and demand for the company's analyst services. It claims that when there is a greater need for an analysis service, more analysts choose to work for that company because they can make money doing so. The point at which the marginal utility to all customers equals the marginal cost to all financial analysts offering services is the equilibrium point for financial analysts who follow that company. Previous research indicates that certain corporate attributes, such as ownership structures, firm size, and business complexity, will impact analysts' coverage of a firm because they will impact the aggregate supply and demand for financial analysis services. Bhushan (1989b); Brennan and Hughes (1991); Barth et al. (2001a,b); Brennan and Bhushan (1990); and Lang and Lundholm (1996) are a few examples.

Both the overall supply and demand for analyst services are likely to be impacted by a firm's ownership. The demand for analyst services would likely decline if ownership were more concentrated. Since non-insiders are the primary source of demand for analyst services, a rise in the proportion of insider shares held (i.e., blockholding) will subsequently lead to a decrease in the overall demand for analyst services, which will result in a smaller analyst following. Conversely, financial analysts are more likely to follow companies with larger institutional holdings (Frankel et al., 2006).

Additionally, analysts are likely to follow large firms, and vice versa, as the overall demand for analyst services is expected to increase as firm size does. Another explanation for why larger companies have a larger number of analysts is that they can reveal more information to the public, creating better information environments. This, in turn, attracts more analysts to make predictions about those companies because their service costs are lower. Furthermore, because they lack the necessary knowledge and experience, investors are probably more in need of investment advice for companies with more intricate operations. But the overall supply will also be impacted by more complex businesses. For example, analysts may have to pay more to acquire information for investment analysis and services in companies with more business lines, which could lead to a decrease in analyst following (Barth et al., 2001; Barron et al., 2002). Because investors are more uncertain about the firms, they are more likely to seek analyst advice, which in turn leads to a higher analyst following. As a result, private information is more valuable for firms with higher earnings variability as a measure of information uncertainty. Due to investor interest and the possibility of future investment banking IPO listings, growth firms typically draw a larger analyst following (Barth et al., 2001). This leads to a high demand for analyst services and, consequently, high analyst coverage.

The Impact of Non-financial Information on Financial Analyst Behaviour

Increased investor following is one of the possible advantages of the higher disclosure level, according to Lang and Lundholm (1996). Companies with more informative disclosures have a larger analyst following, according to Lang and Lundholm (1993). Furthermore, Francis et al. (1998) discover that companies that

disclose non-financial information through conference calls have more analyst coverage. According to [Eccles et al. \(2001\)](#), 75% of financial analysts concur that analyst coverage is enhanced when firms disclose more information. According to [Hope \(2003c\)](#), there is a strong correlation between the amount of note disclosure and analyst coverage. Overall, based on the empirical data presented above, analysts would pay closer attention to companies that increase their level of disclosure and make non-financial disclosures. Analysts are likely to use CSR disclosures in conjunction with financial information as part of their forecasting process because they are a form of non-financial information. This will increase the coverage of the forecast.

CSR disclosures: A Review and discussion

Although different scholars have different classification approaches, the following three methods are used in these studies to measure dependent variables and disclosure quality:

1. The degree of disclosure (proxy approach)
2. A disclosure index determined by the scope, or
3. An index of disclosure based on the depth and breadth (textual analysis)

The term "extent" describes how many words, sentences, pages, or percentage of pages of CSR information businesses include in their reports. The quantity of items a business reports on is referred to as "breadth." This method highlights the reports' content. It does not, however, specify whether or not the items included in the reports are of high quality; it only takes into account those items. The term "depth" describes how specific the disclosure is in reports (i.e., general qualitative versus specific quantitative information). This method takes into account each disclosed item's significance and level of disclosure. Evidence regarding the connection between a firm's attributes and social or environmental disclosures is provided by earlier research. The majority of empirical studies use either a disclosure index based on the breadth of disclosure (e.g., [Cowen et al., 1987](#); [Cormier et al., 2005](#)) or the extent of disclosure (e.g., [Ingram and Wiseman, 1980](#); [Guthrie and Parker, 1989](#); [Zeghal and Ahmed, 1990](#); [Patten, 1992, 1995, 2002](#); [Gray, Kouhy, and Lavers, 1995b](#); [Deegan and Gordon, 1996](#); [Hackston and Milne, 1996](#); [Gray et al., 2001](#)). Studies that use multiple measurement approaches are extremely rare. Recent research on CSR reporting in Malaysian local governments by [Joseph and Taplin \(2011\)](#) shows that various measurement techniques (i.e., extent measures vs. index measures) may produce disparate empirical findings. When taken as a whole, these studies evaluate the disclosure quality on a scale from zero to a maximum. In order to produce more compelling results, this will employ a number of techniques, including extent measures and index measures, for evaluating the quality of CSR disclosure.

A disclosure index based on the breadth

[Patten \(1991\)](#), [Gray et al. \(1995b\)](#), [Hackston and Milne \(1996\)](#), [Adams et al. \(1998\)](#), [Williams and Pei \(1999\)](#), [Purushothaman et al. \(2000\)](#), and [Archel \(2003\)](#) are just a few of the empirical studies in CSR that helped develop the CSR index that is currently in use. The relationship between disclosure and environmental performance was first studied by [Ingram and Frazier in 1980](#). By counting the number of content items included in the annual reports using a check list, they employed a scoring system (rated by the Council on Economic Priorities, or CEP) to gauge the levels of environmental disclosure. [Wiseman \(1982\)](#) measured the quality of environmental disclosures using CEP data and the total score calculated by counting the number of textual items in reports. A raw disclosure score akin to [Wiseman's \(1982\)](#) was employed by [Freedman and Wasley \(1990\)](#). By counting the number of pertinent items disclosed, [Roberts \(1992\)](#) set the disclosure quality

to zero for non-disclosing companies and specific maximum values for disclosing companies. Similar binary methods were also employed by others (see Guthrie and Parker, 1990; Patten, 1991; Hackston and Milne, 1996). Wiseman's textual analysis method is used by Fekrat et al. (1996) to measure the environment's disclosure quality using disclosure indices. Naturally, these studies, which are based on the CEP reports from the early 1970s (Ingram and Frazier, 1980; Wiseman, 1982; Freedman and Wasley, 1990), are restricted to businesses that are assessed solely by the CEP, which leads to sample selection issues. The textual analysis approach, which gives one point for each area of environmental disclosure in financial reports, is also used by Patten (2002). Nevertheless, this study does not account for industry, firm size, or other potentially important factors that may influence disclosure choices. This study restricts the analysis of cross-sectional variation in disclosures because industries are categorized as having high or low disclosure profiles (Brammer and Pavelin, 2006). Additionally, its methodology for measuring environmental disclosures and sample selection are insufficient (Clarkson et al., 2008).

Compared to the extent approach, which uses unreliable proxies, the disclosure index approach based on breadth is better overall because it allows researchers to examine whether the disclosed contents are relevant to the stakeholders. Additionally, it is more reasonable and reliable than other approaches (i.e., proxies for information quality and assurance) because more disclosed items in the reports can give users more information. All of these methods are debatable, though, because researchers are unable to discern between the factors that influence a company's choice to reveal CSR information and the caliber of that disclosure. In order to address this problem, Brammer and Pavelin (2006) offered more useful metrics that specifically include independent dependent variables in disclosure decisions and disclosure quality. They assigned an indicator variable of 1 to a firm's "Disclosure Decision" if it disclosed any of the six environmental items, and 0 to the opposite. In order to gauge a company's disclosure quality, they also tallied the quantity of environmental items revealed in the reports. They thought that by using binary variables 0 or 1, they could differentiate between a company's decision to disclose CSR information and the quality of that disclosure, which ranges from zero to six. This variable separates businesses that disclose environmental information, even if it is very little, from those that don't. The reason for this is that their method still uses Probit analysis to explain the disclosure quality while including non-disclosing companies (which make up about 43% of the sample) in the process, which produces results that are not very compelling. Given the large number of non-disclosing companies in the samples, this situation is more dire. Therefore, this method is also unable to differentiate between the quality of disclosure and the decision to disclose. Because it can take into account the information's content and reflect a more realistic corporate disclosure quality, this approach is superior to proxies for information quality. Thus, this method is used in this research. As previously stated, this method's flaw is that it fails to differentiate between the quality of the disclosure decision.

Disclosure index: depth (textual analysis) and breadth (items)

Although it is more difficult to set disclosure indices, this method is also a disclosure index technique. The sole distinction is that each disclosed item will be given a weight based on how it was presented, whether that presentation was general, specific, or quantitative. For example, earlier research, such as that done by Al-Tuwaijri, Christensen, and Hughes II (2004), measures environmental disclosures by analyzing the text of a company's annual reports. To gauge the depth of disclosures (e.g., a rating of 0 for no disclosures, 1 for non-specific qualitative disclosures, 2 for specific qualitative disclosures, and 3 for quantitative disclosures for each disclosed item), they employ a coding system that counts the number of disclosed items that are pertinent

to stakeholders. Like Wiseman (1982) and Cormier and Magnan (1999, 2003), Aerts and Cormier (2009) also use a coding instrument to measure the firm's environmental disclosure quality. 39 elements make up environmental disclosures, which are divided into 6 categories: laws and regulations, pollution control, sustainable development, environmental management, land remediation and contamination, environmental expenditures and risks, and pollution abatement. Based on whether businesses explicitly describe the quantitative items, the rating ranges from 1 to 3, where 1 denotes discussions in general and 3 denotes quantitative information. This method can combine various data into a single score while taking disclosure depth into account. It also enables researchers to rate the value of disclosure by businesses while making assessments of particular disclosure importance. However, because it is unable to differentiate between disclosure decisions and disclosure quality, it is unreliable. In order to explain disclosure quality, this study keeps adding non-disclosing companies to the model. Because other researchers can replicate the results, some people say the disclosure index technique is trustworthy. There is no barrier to repetition because the scores are taken from printed annual reports, which can stay consistent over time. Researchers can address this issue if they create their own list for their studies. Disclosure indices have been criticized for concentrating on a few pre-identified items and disregarding text that is unrelated to the list. Additionally, the measure of disclosure quality may be sensitive to the selection of items in the checklist (Walker, 2001). Therefore, self-developed check lists will be used in this study.

Hypothesis Development

Disclosure Decision and Analyst Following

If firms decide to disclose more financial or non-financial information to the public, it can likely capture more analysts to follow those firms based on prior works (Lang and Lundholm, 1996; Francis et al., 1998; Eng and Teo, 2000; Eccles et al., 2001; Hope, 2003c; Lang et al., 2003; Bushman, Piotroski, and Smith, 2005; Ali et al., 2005; Weiss, 2010). Besides, according to stakeholder theory, legitimacy theory and Ullmann's framework and previously indicated prior literatures, CSR activities can also affect corporate economic performance. For instance, firms more concern about employee benefit, rights and relations can reduce monitoring costs with employees, improve employees' satisfaction and productivity and attracting better quality staff due to highly reputed organizations. Social initiatives tend to enhance corporate reputation, thereby also indirectly affecting financial performance because consumers are likely to purchase products from those firms and suppliers are likely selling resources to them. Many empirical studies support CSR activities are positively correlated with profitability performance (Akerlof, 1982; Yellen, 1984; Shapiro and Stiglitz, 1984; Margolis, Elfenbein, and Walsh, 2007; Orlitzky, 2008; van Beurden and Gosling, 2008; Carroll and Shabana, 2010; Wood, 2010; Grappi, Romani and Bagozzi, 2013; Sweetin et al, 2013), thereby capturing analysts to follow more firms with decision of disclosing CSR information in their forecasts so that they have more information to predict future earnings. Analysts acquire information with lower costs led to more provision of forecasts and follow those firms more. Besides, Francis et al. (1998) examine and find that there is an increase in analyst coverage for firms making conference calls which are one type of nonfinancial information disclosures. So, this study conjecture that analysts likely follow firms with providing stand-alone CSR disclosure as does other non-financial disclosures. This study followed Brammer and Pavelin's (2006) approach of distinguishing between disclosure decisions and disclosure levels. In order to measure a firm's Disclosure Decision, they used indicator variable 1 in the event that it discloses any one of the six environmental items. Likewise, with regard to disclosure decisions, this study will use a dummy measurement for firms with stand-alone CSR disclosures in a particular year (interest group) and firms without stand-alone CSR disclosure in a particular year (control group), because some firms disclose stand-alone CSR in some years but do not disclose such information during the other years. In the period firms with CSR disclosures, analysts have supplemented CSR information with accounting information to make forecasts, thus resulting

in greater analyst coverage. Moreover, period firms that do not disclose CSR information run the risk of losing analyst following. So, it can predict that there is greater analyst coverage for firms providing CSR disclosure in that year, vice versa.

H1a. Analysts are more likely to follow for firms that provide stand-alone corporate social responsibility reports in particular year.

Disclosure Level and Analyst Following

Expanded financial disclosure level likely provides more valuable information, in turn greater analyst following (Healy and Palepu, 2001). Bhushan (1989a, b) and Lang and Lundholm (1996) also document if increased financial disclosures, firms likely supply more analytical information, thereby greater analyst coverage. According to stakeholder theory, its framework (see last chapter), previously indicated prior literatures (e.g. Sweetin et al., 2013) and many real cases in practice (Nike, Apple etc.), CSR activities can also influence corporate economic performance. For instance, proactive compliance with environmental standards can help firms to prevent certain legal costs in the long term. Firms sponsoring the social events have the potential to change the attendees' attitudes or behavior of consumption since sponsoring events can deepen the consumers' awareness and knowledge of sponsoring firm products, in turn thereby increasing consumers to purchase more firm products and bettering for profitability performance in long term. Many prior studies also show that CSR activities can positively improve firm financial performance (Akerlof, 1982; Yellen, 1984; Shapiro and Stiglitz, 1984; Margolis, Elfenbein, and Walsh, 2007; Orlitzky, 2008; van Beurden and Gossling, 2008; Carroll and Shabana, 2010; Wood, 2010; Grappi, Romani and Bagozzi, 2013; Sweetin et al, 2013), thereby capturing analysts to follow more firms with higher CSR disclosure level as supplementary information with accounting information in their forecasts since analysts' incentive to maximize forecast accuracy try to establish their reputation (Beyer et al., 2010). Therefore, they are likely to use such CSR information to improve their forecast accuracy and reliability.

Regarding non-financial information, there are more financial analysts to capture firms that hold conference calls in which managers can convey much non-financial information to them (Francis et al., 1998) as they can distinguish from other analysts in providing more accurate forecasts to investors. To simplify, if firms disclose more non-financial information, more analysts will follow those firms to gain higher profits from those public information acquisitions. Otherwise, they will face competitive disadvantage with other analysts. Hope (2003c) reports that analyst coverage is highly associated with the extent of note disclosure in the annual reports, indicating that they likely use non-financial disclosures during their forecasting. Hence, this study conjectures that as do other non-financial disclosures (e.g. corporate governance disclosures, note in annual reports, conference calls, etc), firms that increase CSR disclosure level can attract more analysts to follow those firms. The hypothesis is developed as 1b.

H1b. Analysts are more likely to follow for firms that increase stand-alone corporate social responsibility disclosure level, measured by number of pages of corporate social responsibility reports (measurement mentioned in chapter 6 and 7).

Disclosure Quality and Analyst Following

Quality of financial reporting is an important factor to determine usefulness of information for financial analysts (Lang and Lundholm, 1996; Williams, 1996; Healy et al., 1999), in turn influencing analyst following. Some prior works examine how the firm characteristics affect the analysts whether to follow the firms (Chung and Jo, 1996; Botosan and Harris, 2000, Barth, Kasznik and McNichols, 2001). They find that one of the most important factors for analysts to follow the firms is the disclosure quality, suggesting that firms with higher disclosure quality are greater analyst coverage. For instance, Botosan and Harris (2000) find that firm financial disclosure quality is the most important factor to attract analysts to follow those firms. They measure the disclosure quality by the credibility of the report (e.g. audited reports). Moreover, according to stakeholder theory and its framework (see next chapter) and previously indicated prior literatures, CSR activities can also affect corporate financial performance (Akerlof, 1982; Yellen, 1984; Shapiro and Stiglitz, 1984; Margolis, Elfenbein, and Walsh, 2007; Orlitzky, 2008; Beurden and Gossling, 2008; Carroll and Shabana, 2010; Wood, 2010; Grappi, Romani and Bagozzi, 2013; Sweetin et al, 2013), thereby capturing analysts to follow more firms with better CSR disclosure quality as supplementary information with accounting information in their forecasts. One of important disclosure quality is information credibility. So, this study argue that due to CSR activities influencing financial performance and some of CSR reports audited or assured by third parties, for firms with providing better quality of stand-alone corporate social responsibility reports, analysts can benefit more from such credible information for providing more accurate forecasts leading to them more follow those firms. It is because credible CSR information can help them to predict firm future earnings more accurately. For measuring disclosure quality, auditors or independent assurance of corporate disclosures by third party to verify whether companies conform to GAAP and other rules and regulations. Kothari (2001) argues that investors more trust the information provided by auditors due to more credible. Prior works also show that even though regulators do not require financial information to be audited, bankers normally require firms to present audited information for financing purpose, implying that creditable information may also be valuable for stakeholders (Leftwich, 1983). Simnett et al (2009) also provide other measurements for the credibility of corporate social responsibility report, namely assurance by third party (e.g. Environmental Resources Management, URS, Bureau Veritas, Corporate Citizen Coy) and audited by accounting professionals (e.g. Deloitte & Touche, Ernst & Young, KPMG, PWC). They find capital providers would value higher for companies that disclose audited and assured CSR information. As indicated above, if firms can provide audited or assured CSR reports, analysts can make more accurate forecasts using such information to differentiate them from other competitive analysts because analysts have incentive to maximize forecast accuracy to establish their reputations in capital markets (Beyer et al., 2010), thereby resulting in greater analyst coverage for those firms. However, the prior paper, Simnett et al (2009), does not examine how those assured or audited stand-alone CSR reports affect the financial analyst coverage.

H1c. Analysts are likely following for firms with better disclosure quality of corporate social responsibility reports, resulting in having higher forecast accuracy by financial analysts, measured by CSR reports assured or audited by third parties, and disclosure index captured by 89 items of research instrument, including the social and environmental disclosure scores. (the measurement of assurance by third parties and the disclosure index mentioned in later sections)

Estimation of Analyst Coverage

Analyst following is frequently used to proxy for the informativeness of a firm's information environment (Walther 1997; Ayers and Freeman 2003). This study follows the prior studies (e.g. Bhushan, 1989b ; Rock,

Sedo and Willenborg, 2001; Afshad J. Irani and Karamanou, 2003) to compute Analyst Coverage, $COV_{3monthbefore}$, by using the total number of financial analysts who issued the most recent annual earnings forecasts a quarter before earnings announcement in that particular year provided in IBES database.

How quantity approach to measuring CSR quality

The earliest work includes Bowman and Haire (1976); Ernst and Ernst (1978); Trotman (1979); Trotman and Bradley (1981) and Guthrie (1982; 1983). Ernst and Ernst (1978) use different dimensions of research instrument to capture firm social and environment disclosures, including environment, energy, products/consumers, community, employee/human resources, fair business practices, general/other). Bowman and Haire(1976) and Trotman and Bradley (1981) use proportions of pages to capture amount of social information. Guthrie (1982) includes an additional dimension of location in annual report (i.e. chairman's review, separate section, other sections). Other empirical studies also count the number of words or sentences in annual reports devoted to environmental information (e.g. Hackston and Milne, 1996). They highly resemble Gray et al's research instruments. Weber (1990) suggests that the best analytical studies use both qualitative and quantitative operations on their texts. This study therefore considers social and environmental disclosure as comprising both quantitative and qualitative information released through paper-based CSR report platforms. Corporate managers can use social and environmental disclosure as a management tool for influencing stakeholder perceptions through disclosure decisions about the amount of information (i.e., quantity) and the range of topics (i.e., thematic content) to be included in their disclosures (Merkl-Davies and Brennan, 2007). Opinions differ on which proxies are appropriate for use in examining CSR quality in annual reports (Gray et al., 1995b; Milne and Adler, 1999; Beattie et al., 2004). The measures used to evaluate disclosure quantity in prior studies include the number of words, the number of pages, page proportions, and the number of sentences (see table 7.1 below). Using these measures implies the assumption that the quantity of disclosure is a valid proxy for quality of disclosure; the findings suggest that quantity and quality are indeed positively correlated. Quality and quantity are correlated because, when more information is provided to users, they can make better investment decisions.

For instance, when a corporation discloses a significant amount of CSR information, financial analysts can use it to predict the firm's future earnings, in a positive correlation of quantity and quality. For an extreme example, suppose one company issues a one-page CSR report and another company releases a 100-page CSR report; obviously, the second company is providing high CSR quality given the large quantity of data provided for use in analysts' earnings forecasting. All other factors being constant, analysts will likely forecast the second firm accurately because of the information received during the forecasting. Therefore, this is the study's approach. The advantage of this approach is, obviously, that measuring CSR quality is simpler than it is through textual analysis.

Further, many argue that a pure examination of the *quantity* of CSR disclosure in annual reports is too simplistic (Unerman, 1999; Moneva and Llana, 2000) because information quality partly depends on the content itself, rather than just on the quantity of the disclosure. Information quantity is unlikely to be perfectly equivalent to disclosure quality. Take an example, suppose both companies A and B issue the same 100-page CSR reports but company A disclose wider CSR information so that company A disclosure quality is better than company B. Under this approach, however, both companies are treated as same CSR disclosure quality. Further, this approach cannot identify whether the reports are audited by third parties, ignoring the accuracy,

auditability and neutrality assessments³. Besides, researchers do not require reading the content of the reports, thereby never measuring the quality in term of clarity, comparability and relevance. Therefore, this approach is only used for supplementing for disclosure indices as well as assurance.

This study has followed the prior research (e.g., Guthrie and Parker, 1989; Patten, 1992, 1995; Gray, Kouhy, and Lavers, 1995b; Hackston and Milne, 1996; Gray et al., 2001; Patten, 2002) by measuring CSR information through the number of CSR report pages. The pictures and graphics used in CSR reports represent an important issue: we need to consider whether to count those pages. Visual communication (e.g., graphs, tables, pictures) has long been used in annual reports because it is an effective and powerful means of conveying information to users (Beattie and Thomson, 2007). Photographs can also be used to highlight a company's message and influence its audience (Preston et al., 1996). Unerman (2000) argues that any quantification technique that ignores graphics or pictures produces an incomplete picture of disclosure quality. It has also been argued that photographs can serve as a more powerful communication medium in CSR than narratives (Unerman, 2000). Some researchers have investigated only the photographs and charts related to social, environmental, or ethical themes that are designed to influence stakeholders (e.g., Li et al., 2008). However, financial analysts are professional users who are more focusing on the contents including figures and words, instead of the pictures and graphics as the words and figures, are more matter of facts and difficult to be manipulated unlike pictures and graphics. This is just like junior forms of students are likely capturing from and influenced by those pictures and graphics, whereas, senior form students are on average are less likely to be influenced by those. Steenkamp and Northcott (2007) argue that prior studies little provide any suggestion of practical guidance on how to objectively count and interpret graphics. Deegan et al. (2000) argue that it is difficult to objectively measure pictures and diagrams. So, Unerman (2000) supports to include pictures in examination. However, many prior studies would choose to exclude those (SteenKamp and Northcott, 2007) due to the interpretation turns to be subjective (Guthrie et al, 2004). However, the result is not economically significant. So, this study will include all the pages as pictures and graphics are less likely influencing professional analysts.

However, many argue that a pure examination of the *quantity* of CSR disclosure in annual reports is too simplistic (Unerman, 1999; Moneva and Llana, 2000) because information quality partly depends on the content itself, rather than just on the quantity of the disclosure. Information quantity is unlikely to ever be perfectly equivalent to disclosure quality.

How Qualitative approach to measure CSR quality

Disclosure indices

Another way of measurement of CSR quality is via disclosure indices. The earliest work includes Bowman and Haire (1976); Ernst and Ernst (1978); Trotman (1979); Trotman and Bradley (1981) and Guthrie (1982; 1983). One of prior studies using disclosure indices was by Roberts (1991) who looks at the large companies' disclosures in five European countries (France, Germany, the Netherlands, Sweden and Switzerland). Roberts uses a checklist of 54 items capturing the environment or employee-related disclosure matters. Other recent CSR experts prefer to use disclosure indices, including Bewley and Li (2000), Patten (2002), Cormier and Magnan (2003), Al-Tuwaijri et al. (2004), Cormier et al. (2005), Ho and Taylor (2007), Aerts et al. (2008), Branco and Rodrigues (2008) and Aerts and Cormier (2009), in the last decade, which analyzes corporate

³Regarding the detail of Conceptual framework under accounting standards as well as GRI guidance, please refer to Appendix C.

disclosure content and to code as an index that can be either weighted or unweighted.

Weighted and unweighted disclosure indices are arising from corporate disclosure practice as focusing on qualitative or quantitative ways. Honestly, there are different arguments for whether disclosure should be qualitative or quantitative. In CSR disclosure, **Toms (2002)** suggests the qualitative disclosure, providing figures and data as it is difficult for competitors to quantify disclosures benefiting for them. However, **Beattie and Thomson (2006)** argue that it is appropriate to link CSR quality with quantitative information. Unweighted indices only assess the extent of social and environmental content that means only capturing the presence or absence of specific social and environmental contents as well (**Roberts, Weetman and Gordon, 2002**) but ignore to evaluate the content whether disclosed in a general, specific or quantitative way. Thus, academic researchers use a weighted approach to consider not only the presence of each item but also evaluate presentation manners. With regard to both techniques, there is an extensive list of selected social and environmental items which may be disclosed in various disclosure vehicles and a coding indicator will be employed to record the presence or absence of items. The former approach is simplistic as just check the presence of the items according to the provided checklist. The later approach is checking not only presence of the item but also consider the disclosure methods, qualitative or quantitative. If the research question only intends to check the extent of information disclosed, the former is a better way to meet the research question. However, this study is far more than that as this study is to measure how the CSR Quality to affect financial analysts. Financial analysts is not only concerning whether a company disclose information of some CSR activities, such as customers, suppliers, employees, environmental liabilities/ obligations, community donation and so forth, which can affect analysts to predict corporate future earnings but also they more likely information disclosed in monetary terms. Unweighted system lacks of power to measure a corporate CSR quality because the extent of information does not perfectly measure how such information influences analysts' forecasting as the existence of such information does not mean that it can help them to predict earnings. For instance, a company just claims they would like donate to the community but this information not much help financial analysts forecasting. The unweighted system cannot be employed in this study.

Turn to the weighting system, different studies have different weighting techniques. The weighting system is not only a yes/no checklist of items whether the company discloses such item or not. It needs to consider how the company discloses such items in CSR reports. As a financial analyst, he/ she likely prefers information disclosed in a monetary term to qualitative information because analysts' mainly duty is to forecast future earnings. During the forecasting process, financial analysts have to find corporate information from corporate reports to input their forecasting models. One of those reports shall be CSR reports. So, if the information disclosed in monetary terms in CSR reports is likely to aid analysts easier to find out those CSR activities how to affect financial performance in current year or even use figures of those activities over years to predict the impact on future financial performance, thereby more benefiting analysts during forecasting process. So, this study will employ the weighted technique for all items in the checklists. As a financial analyst, obviously, monetary information is better than qualitative information and qualitative CSR information is generally better than non-disclosure. For instance, supposing that both companies X and Z have disclosed all 89 items on the checklist in their stand-alone CSR reports but company X disclose all items in a quantitative/ monetary way, whereas, company Y disclose those in general narratives, it, thus, does not mean they are the same information quality because the company A's CSR information likely more useful and better quality than company B's for financial analysts in forecasting earnings. **Ader (1999)**, an analyst at Bear Stearns, support this view that "The more quantitative information a company can provide to present the dynamic and accounting of the business is a positive change. We obviously understand the protection of competitive information in the role of an

analyst, and I'm sensitive to that. But I think any information that you can provide an investor or analyst that speaks to the primary drivers of revenues and expense and the dynamics of what the primary expenses are helping you to understand really what makes the profits." But how to weight the items is better to refer to CSR prior studies. Many previous studies (e.g. [Bozzolan et al., 2003](#); [Guthrie et al., 2006](#)) employ the weighting system based on whether the CSR information disclosed in quantitative or qualitative terms that can meet this study research purpose. For instance, [Roberts \(1991\)](#) scores "1" for a company that discloses only qualitative checklist items, scores "3" for a company that discloses information about the same activities but provides quantitative data and scored "5" for a company that also present financial data covering several years. [Guthrie et al \(2006\)](#) use an indicated variable, namely 0, 1, 2, and 3, for non-disclosure, disclosure of a descriptive nature, disclosure in a numerical form and items disclosed in currency terms, respectively. [Bozzolan et al \(2003\)](#) just assign 0 for non-disclosure, 1 for qualitative information and 2 for quantitative information. [Striukova et al \(2008\)](#) examines different types of CSR disclosure regarding momentary quantified, non-monetary quantified and narrative disclosures then assign the weighting. All prior studies also compare the score received by a company with the maximum score it could have got to produce a measure of the relative level of disclosure. This study will employ [Bozzolan et al's \(2003\)](#), [Guthrie et al's \(2006\)](#) and [Striukova et al's \(2008\)](#) technique because these weighting is the most common and popular for the researchers in the prior studies and this is relatively simplistic and fewer errors occurring during the coding process to capture the impact of CSR quality on financial analysts. However, [Roberts et al \(2002\)](#) argue that if the checklist contains "a fairly large number of items of information, a company that scores relatively high on an equally weighted scoring system will also usually score relatively high on any other type of weighted scoring system". However, after considering financial analysts actually prefer monetary/ quantitative information rather than qualitative/ narrative information, this study will stick to the weighting system.

To implement the disclosure index approach, another thing needs to be considered, namely the research instrument, which is the most important in this approach as it is poor, resulting in more likely influencing the validity of results. Numerous prior studies suggest different checklists to perform textual analysis. The methodology includes to use weighting and unweighting systems. Some researchers just focus on one country, whereas, others investigate multi-countries, resulting in various disclosure patterns in different countries. For examination of disclosure vehicles, prior studies also more focus on annual reports, social and environmental reports, CSR reports and some would examine corporate websites in recent years. The checklist also varies from studies to studies as many of them only investigate either social or environmental aspects, on the contrary, some of them would investigate both. Further, even if some researchers examine the same social disclosure quality, they always use different categories such as customers, suppliers, community, employees and so on. Regarding the research instrument, earliest studies already developed some dimensions on social and environment. [Ernst and Ernst \(1978\)](#) use various dimensions of a research instrument to capture firm social and environment disclosures, including environment, energy, products/consumers, community, employee/human resources, fair business practices, general/other. [Guthrie \(1982\)](#) further includes an additional dimension of location in annual report (i.e. chairman's review, separate section, other sections). [Gray et al. \(1995b\)](#) later modify Guthrie's research instrument by removing the dimension location in annual report, adding a further dimension of value added statement and including environment policies and environment audit⁴. [Hackston and Milne's \(1996\)](#) instrument highly resembles Gray et al.'s version. This study

⁴Numerous prior studies have been examining CSR assurance and audit (e.g. [O'Dwyer and Owen, 2005; 2007](#); [Cooper and Owen, 2007](#); [Mock, Strohm, and Swartz, 2007](#); [Darnall, Seol, and Sarkis, 2009](#); [Simmnett et al., 2009](#); [Kolk and Perego, 2010](#)).

will adopt all those dimensions. This approach just adopts the list from a prior study but it may not suit to the specific research question. For instance, a checklist designed for examining a country's social and environmental disclosures may not be applicable in another country. For instance, for example, the US corporate CSR reports such as Cisco, Microsoft have not much mentioned financial performance, whereas, France corporate CSR reports such as AirFrance usually discuss those on it. Besides, a checklist designed for examining CSR in annual reports may not be applicable in other vehicles. Even though both studies investigate social disclosure quality, they may have different research purposes. Perhaps, one may examine the impact of CSR quality on financial performance; another may examine the determinants to CSR quality. It is difficult for a researcher to directly adopt a checklist for his research. However, this approach can compare the result with prior studies and can let future researchers replicate his research. This adoption approach will not be employed in this study as considering this specific research question to investigate the impact of CSR quality on analysts. So, analysts' concern may differ from others. This study would select corporate social and environmental disclosure items from those recent prior studies but not purely only adopt from one paper. The benefit of this approach is the researcher can develop his own checklist to suit his research question. In this study, prior studies are selected from the most popular checklist of prior studies published in top journals in last decade, including *Journal of Accounting and Public Policy*; *Accounting, Organizations and Society*; *Journal of Management Studies*; *Journal of Business Finance & Accounting*; *Journal of International Financial Management and Accounting*; *Journal of Business Ethics*; *European Accounting Review*; *Ecological Economics*; *Accounting Forum*; *Advances in Environmental Accounting & Management*. When selecting the items from the checklist for this study, it should consider what kind of CSR information is concerned by financial analysts or what information they want. The financial analysts' main duty⁵ is to provide various forecasts, such as earnings, cash flow, revenues and so on, to intermediaries, buy-side analysts and general investors. A journal performs a survey with financial analysts asking them what kind of information they need the most, in which most of the financial analysts express that product line; forward-looking; strategic; segment data; key business risks and uncertainties; the competitive strategy; financial liquidity and flexibility; an identification of the corporate strategy (Strategic Finance, 1999). Though incomplete, the segment data does provide significant additional insights into the past operating performance of the company and its segments and insight into possible future performance. Further, an effective way to link management actions and the company's financial results is to use nonfinancial performance metrics that tie a company's current actions to its future performance. So, if such CSR company actions can influence current and future economic performance of the company, there are more likely capturing financial analysts to use such information from CSR reports in their forecasting. Therefore, selecting the checklist items would be based on above factors. Initially, the numbers of disclosed items are initially more than 150 in this study. However, some companies are also extracting financial information (e.g. dividend, earnings per share, revenues and costs, operating income) presented in CSR reports such as Nike, AirFrance⁶, Marks and Spencers and so on. None of these should be in the list of potential corporate social responsibility items. Besides, prior studies also include financial items⁷

⁵Strategic Finance find that 91% of financial analysts believe that they are getting the information they need to forecast future financial performance.

⁶It provides distribution of group revenue, expenses and profit from operation in different sectors and locations and some operation data in 2011 CSR report.

⁷ E.g. Increase in sales/market shares; Earnings or sales forecasts; Sales – new products; Gross margin; Production cost; Net operating income; REA or REO; EPS (diluted); Dividend distributions; Reengineering/downsizing; Size and types of major tangible investments; Economic

in the checklists which raise a problem that financial analysts will normally read such information in annual reports rather than CSR reports, thereby the impact of CSR quality on analysts may not be so clear. Those financial items disclosed in CSR reports should be therefore excluded from the checklist. Otherwise, it is difficult to distinguish the impact on analysts being resulted from either CSR reports or annual reports. More importantly, prior studies have not fully considered and incorporated the CSR items outlined by GRI framework. GRI produces the corporate social responsibility reporting standards by all companies as routine as, and comparable to, financial reporting. GRI Guidelines are widely used because more than 5,332 companies⁸ from 60 countries use the Guidelines to prepare and present their corporate social responsibility reports. According to the database, those companies have totally issued 13,954 stand-alone CSR reports in which 12,019 reports are based on GRI guidance. Its guidance is also applied to public agencies, small business enterprises, non-profit organizations, interest groups and municipal governments. The goal of GRI is to develop a generally accepted reporting framework, namely The GRI Sustainability Reporting Guidelines, to enhance the usefulness of CSR reports by stakeholders. This study also needs to review again what items recommended by GRI are useful for this study so as to better measure corporate CSR quality and its impact on analysts. For this reason, this study includes 2 additional labor issue items, namely “Health and Safety Committees” and “Type of Injury and rates of Injury/ Incident rate”; 1 public sector item, namely “Monetary Value of Significant Fines for Non-Compliance with laws”; 2 items of environmental disclosures, namely “Transporting products, materials pollution” and “Total weight of waste by type and disposal method”⁹.

After considering some items are quite similar each other, so, this study consolidates as one. For instance, Land remediation and contamination: Sites, Remediation efforts, Potential liability-remediation, Implicit liability, and Spills are combined as Land remediation and contamination. Items are excluded from the list mainly due to no, less or just indirect financial impact on corporations, or too general, or not a CSR item and irrelevant and no interests for analysts in forecasting (e.g. this study deletes “Accident rate” used by prior studies). The completed checklist (89 items) has been created for this study in *Table 1*. However, most of prior studies of disclosure index have a common problem that their result cannot distinguish the disclosure decision from disclosure quality since the non-disclosing companies being incorporated in an ordinary-least-square (OLS) analysis to explain disclosure quality, resulting in unconvincing results. For the case that corporation, the corporation is likely to engage such specific CSR activity but opt to not disclose such activity information, this study will be classified as “No disclosure”. After considering disclosure decision and different extent of disclosure quality, there are three made cases adopted in this study, including, “no disclosure”, “disclosure in narrative/ qualitative”, and “disclosure in quantitative” in *Table 2*.

performance of major tangible investments; Other intangible investments; R&D investments; Information about size and profitability; Liquidity; Indebtedness; Interest coverage; Stock price or stock return; Investment (\$); Increase in investments; Market share – new products; Process improvement methods (ex. Kaizen); ISO 9000, total quality management – TQM; Production capacity; Production Waste; Inventory/run out rate; Quality of equipment and technology; Flexibility of capacity; Process description; etc.

⁸ From the sustainability disclosure database: <http://database.globalreporting.org/>

⁹Please refer *Table 4* in more detail.

Table 1: Raw Checklist items of this study

	Sources		Reasons
General			
Strategic planning	Aerts et al (2008)	included	corporate strategy influence future corporate image and indirectly affect interests of analysts
Goals and targets for environment	Aerts & Cormier (2009)	included	key business risks
Risk management	Aerts et al (2008)	included	forward-looking
Partnerships	Aerts et al (2008)	excluded	no related
Leadership	Aerts et al (2008)	excluded	no related
Mission	Aerts et al (2008)	excluded	
Product			
Product description	Aerts et al (2008)	excluded	not a CSR item
Product safety	Branco and Rodrigues (2008), Aerts et al (2008), Gao et al (2005)	included	financial impact supported by Berman, S. L., (1999)
Product quality	Branco and Rodrigues (2008), Aerts et al (2008), Gao et al (2005)	included	product line & affect financial performance support by Ittner (1998)
Product Price	Aerts et al (2008)	included	financial impact
Energy efficiency of products	Branco and Rodrigues (2008), GRI EN7	included	Product line & profitability financial impact supported by Anderson (1997)
Product Delivery time	Aerts et al (2008)	included	
Product testing	Aerts et al (2008)	excluded (less important)	potential future impact
Production time	Aerts et al (2008)	excluded	not a CSR item
Unplanned downtime	Aerts et al (2008)	excluded	not a CSR item
Pre-sales support: information/counsel/orders follow-up	Aerts et al (2008)	included	Revenue impact supported by Molina-Azorín et al (2009)
After-sales service/insurance	Aerts et al (2008)	included	Revenue impact supported by Perera (1997)
Products in development stage	Aerts et al (2008)	included	future profit influence
Investments in R&D of new product	Aerts et al (2008)	included	future profit influence

Customers

Disclosing of consumer safety practices	Branco and Rodrigues (2008), GRI PR2, 1	excluded	not relevant for corporate financial impact supported by Anderson (1997)
Consumer complaints/satisfaction	Branco and Rodrigues (2008), GRI PR8, PR5	included	
Compensation to customers	Gao et al (2005)	excluded	not relevant for corporate Business risk and uncertainties
Legal proceedings, litigation and liabilities	Gao et al (2005), GRI PR7	included	
Market segment/market share/number of customers	Aerts et al (2008)	included	financial impact financial impact supported by Loveman, G. W. (1998)
Customer loyalty	Aerts et al (2008)	included	
Provision for disabled, aged, and difficult-to-reach consumers	Branco and Rodrigues (2008)	excluded (less important)	influence corporate image and indirectly affect interests of analysts
Other fair business practice disclosure	Gao et al (2005)	excluded (less important)	influence corporate image and indirectly affect interests of analysts
E-business sales	Aerts et al (2008)	excluded	not a CSR item
E-business productivity	Aerts et al (2008)	excluded	not a CSR item
Service Internet	Aerts et al (2008)	excluded	not a CSR item
Internet Impact (award, number of users or visitors)	Aerts et al (2008)	excluded	not a CSR item

Suppliers

Information on major suppliers	Sources Ho and Taylor (2007)	included	Reasons for predicting cost & supply sufficiency & likely not in Annual report
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Employee

Employee development/training programs	Sources Gao et al (2005), Branco and Rodrigues (2008), Ho and Taylor (2007), GRI LA9 & 10 & HR2	included	Reasons financial impact supported by Russell, Terborg, and Powers (1985)
Employee assistance/benefits	Branco and Rodrigues (2008), Gao et al (2005), Ho and Taylor (2007), GRI LA2	included	financial impact
Employee remuneration	Branco and Rodrigues (2008), Gao et al (2005), Ho and Taylor (2007), Gray et al (1995b), GRI LA13	included	financial impact supported by (Zhuang, J., and Xu, C., 1996).
Employee profiles (e.g. education)	Branco and Rodrigues (2008), Gray et al (1995b), Ho and Taylor (2007)	included	financial impact

Employee morale/ job satisfaction	Branco and Rodrigues (2008)	included	financial impact & Business risks supported by Ruf et al (2001)
Employee share ownership scheme	Gao et al (2005), Gray et al (1995b), Ho and Taylor (2007), Branco and Rodrigues (2008)	included	financial impact supported by Bhargava, S. (1994).
Health and safety at work	Gao et al (2005), Gray et al (1995b), Ho and Taylor (2007), Branco and Rodrigues (2008), GRI LA3 & 8	included	financial impact supported by Smallman, C., & John, G. (2001).
Health and Safety Committees	GRI LA5	included	GRI LA5
Type of Injury and rates of Injury/ Incident rate	GRI LA6 & 7	included	GRI LA6 & 7
Economic Value added statements	Gray et al (1995b), Aerts et al (2008)	included	financial impact
Payroll information by countries or regions	Ho and Taylor (2007)	included	segment data
Fringe benefits information by countries or regions	Ho and Taylor (2007)	included	segment data
Number of employees and their geographic distribution	Ho and Taylor (2007), GRI LA1	included	segment data
Turnover of workforce	Ho and Taylor (2007), GRI LA1	included	financial impact supported by Huselid, M. A. (1995).
Employment of disabled;	Gray et al (1995b), Gao et al (2005)	excluded	no financial impact
Employment of women (sexual equality)	Gao et al (2005), Ho and Taylor (2007), Branco and Rodrigues (2008), GRI LA12	excluded (less important)	potential impact on financial performance supported by Gul et al (2013)
Employment of minority (racial equality)	Gao et al (2005), Ho and Taylor (2007), Branco and Rodrigues (2008)	excluded (less important)	it likely influences corporate image, thereby potential impact on performance
Any mention of policies or programs addressing workplace	Ho and Taylor (2007)	included	Financial impact supported by Huselid, M. A. (1995).
Policies or procedures dealing with human rights issues	Ho and Taylor (2007), GRI HR9	excluded	less interest for analysts (may affect their perceptions)
Number of incidents of Violations	GRI HR8	excluded (less important)	less financial impact (affect corporate image and industrial unrest)
Discrimination and corrective actions taken	GRI HR3	excluded (less important)	influence corporate image and indirectly affect interests of analysts
Sport and recreation for employee	Gao et al (2005)	excluded (less important)	influence corporate image and indirectly affect interests of analysts
Consultation with employees;	Gray et al (1995b)	excluded	no interest for analysts
No. of Grievances about Labor disputes resolved	GRI HR12, 16	excluded (less important)	influence corporate image and indirectly affect interests of analysts
South Africa	Gray et al (1995b)	excluded (less important)	less financial impact

Industrial relations	Branco and Rodrigues (2008)	excluded (less important)	less financial impact (affect corporate image and industrial unrest)
Corporate Governance	Sources		Reasons
Independence Board	Aerts et al (2008)	included	Independence and performance are correlated supported by Beasley, M. S. (1996): information relevant for analysts
Competence Audit committee	Aerts et al (2008)	included	Influence earnings accuracy (Rahman, R. A., & Ali, F. H. M., 2006).
Independence Audit committee	Aerts et al (2008)	included	Independence and earnings accuracy supported by Abbott et al.(2003) strategical information relevant for analyst
Relations with external auditors	Aerts et al (2008)	included	influence how to corporate earnings to predict future earnings
Relations with internal auditors	Aerts et al (2008)	included	influence how to corporate earnings to predict future earnings
Ownership structure	Aerts et al (2008)	included	influence monitoring effectiveness and financial performance (Demsetz, H., and Villalonga, B., 2001)
Directors' Compensation (stocks/options)	Aerts et al (2008)	included	influence financial performance (Zahra, S. A., and Pearce, J. A., 1989)
Public sectors	Sources		Reasons
Taxes by sectors or countries	Ho and Taylor (2007)	included	Segmental data for analysts may affect corporate image and indirectly affect interest of analysts
Discussion of social capital formation	Ho and Taylor (2007)	excluded (less important)	
Monetary Value of Significant Fines for Non-Compliance with laws	GRI PR9, SO8	included	financial impact
Communities	Sources		Reasons
Charitable donations and activities	Branco and Rodrigues (2008), Aerts et al (2008), Gao et al (2005), Gray et al (1995b)	included	financial impact supported by Brammer, S. and Millington, A. (2008).
Support for community & activities	Branco and Rodrigues (2008), Aerts et al (2008), Gao et al (2005), Gray et al (1995b)	included	financial impact & business risk
Political donation and service	Gao et al (2005), GRI SO 6	included	financial impact & business risk

Carrier opportunities	Aerts et al (2008)	excluded	not interest for analysts
Community Award	Aerts et al (2008)	excluded	not interest for analysts
No. of Grievances about Impacts on Society	GRI SO11	excluded (less important)	influence future corporate image and indirectly affect interests of analysts
Significant Negative impacts on Society in the Supply Chain	GRI SO10	excluded (less important)	influence future corporate image and indirectly affect interests of analysts
Corruption policies, incidents and Actions Taken	GRI SO5, SO4, SO3	excluded (less important)	influence future corporate image and indirectly affect interests of analysts
operation negatively impact on community	GRI SO1, 2	excluded (less important)	influence future corporate image and indirectly affect interests of analysts
Integrity and ethics	Sources		Reasons
Policies for compliance mechanisms for bribery and corruption	Ho and Taylor (2007)	included	forward-looking
Policies for preventing anti-competitive behavior	Ho and Taylor (2007), GRI SO7	excluded (less important)	potential financial performance if it has anti competitive
Provision of business code	Ho and Taylor (2007)	excluded (less important)	potential financial impact as may affect analysts' perception towards corporate
Environmental (Environment performance affect financial performance: Griffin, 1997) Strategic	Sources		Reasons
Corporate commitment to environmental protection	Gray et al (1995b), Ho and Taylor (2007), Branco and Rodrigues (2008), Aerts & Cormier (2009)	included	strategical information
Mention environmental rules and regulations	Ho and Taylor (2007), Branco and Rodrigues (2008)	included	strategical information
Involvement of environmental experts in business operations	Ho and Taylor (2007)	included	strategical: prevent future environmental problem
Incorporation of environmental concerns into business decisions for all aspects	Ho and Taylor (2007)	included	reduce future risk
Specific department are assigned to deal with the environment	Aerts & Cormier (2009)	included	strategical information
Involvement of the firm to develop environmental standards	Aerts & Cormier (2009)	excluded	no influence on financial performance
Involvement of environmental organizations in the industry committees	Aerts & Cormier (2009)	excluded	no influence on financial performance

Joint environmental management projects with other firms	Aerts & Cormier (2009)	included	strategical information
Environmental policy	Gao et al (2005), Branco and Rodrigues (2008)	included	strategical information: influencing firm future risk
Environmental management system	Branco and Rodrigues (2008), Aerts & Cormier (2009)	included	strategical information
Environmental accounting policies	Ho and Taylor (2007)	included	strategical information
Environmental audit	Gao et al (2005), Ho and Taylor (2007), Branco and Rodrigues (2008), Aerts & Cormier (2009)	included	Reduce potential Risk in future
Pollution			
Water usage information	Ho and Taylor (2007), GRI EN 1, EN8 & 9	included	Profitability influence
Energy usage information	Gao et al (2005), Ho and Taylor (2007), Branco and Rodrigues (2008), GRI EN1, 3 - 5	included	Profitability influence
Encouragement of renewable energy consumption	Gao et al (2005), Gao et al (2005), Ho and Taylor (2007)	included	key business risks and uncertainties
Conservation of natural resources	Gao et al (2005), Branco and Rodrigues (2008), Aerts & Cormier (2009), GRI EN6	included	key business risks and uncertainties
The materials that are re-cycled or re-used	Ho and Taylor (2007), Branco and Rodrigues (2008), Aerts & Cormier (2009)	included	Profitability influence & business risks & supported by GRI EN2
Any mention of strategies for the use of recycling product	Ho and Taylor (2007)	included	key business risks and uncertainties
Noise and odours	Aerts & Cormier (2009)	included	key business risks and uncertainties
Land remediation and contamination	Aerts & Cormier (2009)	included	key business risks and uncertainties & supported by GRI EN24
Prevention of environmental damage	Gao et al (2005)	included	prevent potential business risks
Transporting products, materials pollution	GRI EN30	included	influence future corporate image and indirectly affect interests of analysts
Pollution control			
Information about the sources, types and remedy procedures of emissions	Ho and Taylor (2007), Aerts & Cormier (2009)	included	key business risks and uncertainties & supported by GRI framework EN15 - 21
Pollution impacts	Ho and Taylor (2007), Branco and Rodrigues (2008), Branco and Rodrigues (2008)	included	key business risks and uncertainties

Environmental impacts of principal products and services	Ho and Taylor (2007)	included	product line
waste management	Ho and Taylor (2007), Aerts & Cormier (2009)	included	key business risks and uncertainties
Waste recycling	Gao et al (2005)	included	profitability & uncertainties
Installation and process controls	Aerts & Cormier (2009)	included	reduce potential risks
Total weight of waste by type and disposal method	GRI framework	included	influence future corporate image and indirectly affect interests of analysts
Financial Impacts			
Environmental expenditures (capital/operating)	Ho and Taylor (2007)	included	financial impact & supported by GRI EN31
Fines/lawsuits/non-compliance incidents	Ho and Taylor (2007), Aerts & Cormier (2009)	included	financial impact & supported by GRI EN29
Environmental contingent liabilities	Ho and Taylor (2007), Aerts & Cormier (2009)	included	financial liquidity and flexibility
Prevention or repair of damage to the environment	Gao et al (2005), Branco and Rodrigues (2008)	included	key business risks and uncertainties
Environmental aesthetics	Branco and Rodrigues (2008)	excluded	no financial impact/ no interest of analysts
Investments for environment	Aerts & Cormier (2009)	included	forward-looking
Environmental Operation costs	Aerts & Cormier (2009)	included	financial impact
Environmental Future investments	Aerts & Cormier (2009)	included	forward-looking
Future Environmental operating costs	Aerts & Cormier (2009)	included	forward-looking
Financing for investments Sites	Aerts & Cormier (2009)	included	financial liquidity and flexibility
Environmental debts	Aerts & Cormier (2009)	included	financial liquidity and flexibility
Provision for future expenditures	Aerts & Cormier (2009)	included	forward-looking
Risk provisions	Aerts & Cormier (2009)	included	key business risks and uncertainties
Corrective action	Aerts & Cormier (2009)	included	key business risks and uncertainties
Future legislation and regulations	Aerts & Cormier (2009), Branco and Rodrigues (2008)	included	forward-looking & uncertainties
Others			
Compliance status of facilities	Aerts & Cormier (2009)	included	key business risks and uncertainties
Life cycle information	Aerts & Cormier (2009)	included	product line

Identification of a contact person for providing additional information	Branco and Rodrigues (2008)	excluded	no interest for analysts influence corporate image and indirectly affect interests of analysts
Sustainability: General	Branco and Rodrigues (2008)	included	
Energy: general	Gray et al (1995b)	excluded	too general cannot identify
CSR Awards	Aerts & Cormier (2009)	excluded	no interest for analysts

Table 2: Research Instruments for this study

	no disclosure (1)	Disclosure in qualitative (2)	Disclosure in quantitative (3)	
General				
Strategic planning				
Goals and targets for environment				
Risk management				
Product				
Product safety				
Product quality				
Product Price				
Energy efficiency of products				
Product Delivery time				
Pre-sales support: information/counsel/orders follow-up				
After-sales service/insurance				
Products in development stage				
Investments in R&D of new product				
Customers				
Consumer complaints/satisfaction				

Legal proceedings, litigation and liabilities				
Market segment/market share/number of customers				
Customer loyalty				
Suppliers				
Information on major suppliers				
Employee				
Employee development/training programs				
Employee assistance/benefits				
Employee remuneration				
Employee profiles (e.g. education)				
Employee morale/ job satisfaction				
Employee share ownership scheme				
Health and safety at work				
Health and Safety Committees				
Type of Injury and rates of Injury/ Incident rate				
Economic Value added statements				
Payroll information by countries or regions				
Fringe benefits information by countries or regions				
Number of employees and their geographic distribution				
Turnover of workforce				
Any mention of policies or programs addressing workplace				
Corporate Governance				
Independence Board				
Competence Audit committee				

Independence Audit committee				
Relations with external auditors				
Relations with internal auditors				
Ownership structure				
Directors' Compensation (stocks/options)				
Public sectors				
Taxes by sectors or countries				
Monetary Value of Significant Fines for Non-Compliance with laws				
Communities				
Charitable donations and activities				
Support for community & activities				
Political donation and service				
Integrity and ethics				
Policies for compliance mechanisms for bribery and corruption				
Environmental (Environment performance affect financial performance: Griffin, 1997)				
Strategical				
Corporate commitment to environmental protection				
Mention environmental rules and regulations				
Involvement of environmental experts in business operations				
Incorporation of environmental concerns into business decisions for all aspects				
Specific department are assigned to deal with the environment				
Joint environmental management projects with other firms				

Environmental policy				
Environmental management system				
Environmental accounting policies				
Environmental audit				
Pollution				
Water usage information				
Energy usage information				
Encouragement of renewable energy consumption				
Conservation of natural resources				
The materials that are re-cycled or re-used				
Any mention of strategies for the use of recycling product				
Noise and odours				
Land remediation and contamination				
Prevention of environmental damage				
Transporting products, materials pollution				
Total weight of waste by type and disposal method				
Pollution control				
Information about the sources, types and remedy procedures of emissions				
Pollution impacts				
Environmental impacts of principal products and services				
waste management				
Waste recycling				
Installation and process controls				
Financial Impacts				

Environmental expenditures (capital/ operating)				
Fines/lawsuits/non-compliance incidents				
Environmental contingent liabilities				
Prevention or repair of damage to the environment				
Investments for environment				
Environmental Operation costs				
Environmental Future investments				
Future Environmental operating costs				
Financing for investments Sites				
Environmental debts				
Provision for future expenditures				
Risk provisions				
Corrective action				
Future legislation and regulations				
Others				
Compliance status of facilities				
Life cycle information				
Sustainability: General				

How Assurance to measure CSR quality

Many of accounting firms have translated their core knowledge, experience and expertise in financial auditing to successfully develop a new revenue-generating market in social and environmental auditing in past two decades (Power, 1997, 2003). That audited financial information is regarded as high credible information, thereby useful for decision makers. Whereas, this study can also use another measure for CSR quality, namely whether CSR reports are audited and assured or not. This technique can likely assess certain qualitative characteristics of information because it can quantify the credibility of accounting information as a binary variable. When the corporate accounting information is audited by big-4 or other non-financial information is assured by the third party, the information represents as high credible, indicating better information quality. What is more, auditors also assess all other qualitative characteristics of corporate information, such as reliability, freedom from bias, verifiability, representational faithfulness, neutrality, and comparability conform to standards. This approach can, therefore, widely measure accounting information quality. Some CSR experts suggest that auditing or assurance can contribute to reliability and consistency of CSR information (European Commission's Expert Group on Disclosure of Non-Financial information by EU Companies, 2011). Additionally, based on the GRI framework, this approach can assess CSR information in term of auditability, accuracy and neutrality. For example, this approach can identify whether the reports are audited by third parties, capturing the accuracy, auditability and neutrality attributes of information since those have to be assessed by the auditors. So, as first two approaches (i.e. proxies of information quality and disclosure indices) only consider relevance, transparency, inclusiveness and completeness of information quality but ignore other critical quantitative characteristics of information, namely reliability, auditability and neutrality thus this study incorporating it as supplemented with other two. More importantly, an official document, namely annual reports, is always reviewed by auditors and filed with securities regulators but CSR reports do not, thereby valuably examining CSR quality through assurance. In empirical studies, [Hunton et al. \(2006\)](#) suggest that the disclosure quality likely reflects the reliability of the disclosure. Further, credible reports are likely to reflect better disclosure quality and in turn more informative to analysts ([Teoh and Wong 1993](#); [Wilson 2008](#)), resulting in more analysts following those firms, higher accurate forecasts and less dispersed forecasts. So, if CSR reports are assured or audited by a third party, it presents higher information quality, resulting in greater analyst coverage, higher forecast accuracy and less forecast dispersions. So, this study will employ this approach.

To measure the extent of the disclosure quality by auditing, in most studies to date, differences in the quality of assurance services provided have been studied by examining differences between the use of Big 4 firms and non-Big 4 firms. It can be argued that the Big 4 audit firms possess scale economies and greater capacity to invest in new technologies for auditing, thereby providing higher information quality for the reports. They also have a greater investment in maintaining their reputational capital. As a result, they are better able to serve as an effective monitoring mechanism than are smaller auditors ([DeAngelo 1981](#); [Watts and Zimmerman 1986](#)). However, assurance of financial reports is different from assurance of corporate social responsibility reports because the monopoly may not exist in the assurance of the corporate social responsibility reports. Due to the unregulated assurance market on the corporate social responsibility reports, other assurance providers may be also hired for assurance of CSR reports instead of engagement with auditing firms. [Simnett et al. \(2009\)](#) find evidence suggesting that the use of assurance services is related to the incentive of firms to increase the credibility of their CSR reporting. Further, other assurance specialist providers that are not members of the auditing profession may also possess a higher level of subject-matter expertise to increase the credibility of the firm CSR reports. However, after considering the sample sizes of FT Global 500 companies, many of that did not issue any corporate social responsibility reports and even though those companies that issue corporate social responsibility reports, they are not fully assuring or auditing their corporate social

responsibility reports, thus the fact that this study not classifies members of the auditing profession and other assurance providers. This study will assign 1 for a company that hires either Big-4 or other assurance specialist expertise for its CSR report.

Combination of approaches

Although most of the prior studies only employ a technique (e.g. Only a number of words, sentences, pages, documents, disclosure indices, and assurance), as a section mentioned before, this is only considered a particular qualitative characteristic of information, thereby resulting in difficulty in generalizing a conclusion whether a company is disclosing a good CSR quality or not, compared with other companies, some researchers also employ more than one at once. For instance, **Loughran and McDonald (2011)** employ a weighting scheme to address three components: the importance of a term within a document (measured by proportional occurrence or the frequency); some form of normalization for document length (number of pages) and the importance of a term within the entire reports (typically measured by inverse document frequency). Therefore, this study use three main proxies for capturing disclosure quality including the number of pages of corporate social responsibility reports, auditing or assurance of corporate social responsibility reports and the disclosure index of a 89-item research instrument of corporate social responsibility reports, thereby reflecting corporate social responsibility report disclosure quality.

How to Quantify Disclosure Decision

This study examines whether CSR disclosure decision and disclosure quality affect analyst coverage. Firstly, it is necessary to establish whether or not a company discloses any CSR information. When annual reports are being considered, this is quite a complex process. For example, **Brammer and Pavelin's (2006)** used an indicator variable 1 in the event that it discloses any one of the six environmental items. However, using this approach, the company seems likely to have close results since most of the companies nowadays would more or less disclose certain CSR information in annual reports and seriously, prior studies have used it for a long time only for CSR information presented in the annual reports of the disclosure vehicle but not much for the stand-alone CSR reports. As many researchers have already performed the examination of CSR disclosure quality in the annual reports which is not my research question concerned, thereby this study simplifying this approach to suit the research question to examine the standalone CSR report impacts on financial analysts. In fact, the treatment group indeed consists of firm-years with firms that issue at least one stand-alone CSR report in that particular year (dummy variable = 1); and the control group consists of firm-years with firms that do not issue any stand-alone CSR report in that particular year (dummy variable =0), even if they do disclose CSR information in their annual reports. By doing so, it can compare the analyst behaviour in a group of issuing standalone reports and a group of without issuing standalone reports in a particular year.

However, the technique applied by the prior studies, as above indicated, to examine the corporate CSR decision is not applicable in stand-alone disclosure vehicle so that this study revises the approach to suit the stand-alone CSR disclosure vehicle in measuring disclosure decisions. Therefore, it can be argued that analyst coverage, forecasts, accuracy, and dispersion are likely affected by a firm's CSR disclosure decision (to disclose or not to disclose) in different years. In the period firms with CSR disclosures, CSR information can contribute to analysts in forecasting, thus resulting in greater analyst coverage, lower forecast errors and lower forecast dispersion. Moreover, in the period firms that do not disclose CSR information run the risk of losing analyst following, are less accurate with regard to forecasting, and are less certain about forecast dispersions (**Bhushan, 1989b; Francis et al., 1997; Healy et al., 1999; Lang and Lundholm, 1996**). This approach can only determine the impact of disclosure

decisions on analyst behaviour and isolate the impact of a firm's disclosure quality by using standalone dummy variable and later will use disclosure scores to capture the corporate social and environmental disclosure performance of corporate social responsibility reports.

Type of reports under examination

Conducting an analysis study of CSR issues has two important questions must be answered: (1) what documents to analyze, and (2) how to measure disclosures. Many empirical research studies are analyzing the corporate report (s) for disclosures in respect of one or more categories of social, environmental and/or ethical matters. This section will review prior studies what documents that are examined in respect of CSR disclosures. It is very likely the document(s) examined can determinate the CSR disclosure level and the validity of the results.

Many researchers argue that annual reports are regarded as important documents in CSR since it can provide the high degree of credibility information to the public (Tilt, 1994). Further, due to annual reports usually more accessible to researchers than other corporate reports, there should be one annual report for each company in each year studied (Woodward, 1998). Therefore, annual reports are commonly used documents to analyze to measure the CSR disclosures issues. However, Unerman (1999) argue that most of the studies (see the table 7.7. in more details) focusing exclusively on annual reports risk capturing an incomplete picture of the amount of CSR companies are engaging in, and thus an incomplete picture of the practices they are studying. It is because some companies have disclosed such information in other media such as the press release, websites and so on. Unerman (1999) also engage a case study to investigate the problem of researchers just investigating the CSR disclosures based on the annual reports. In many years the annual report contained less CSR than was contained in other corporate reports, and fluctuations in volumes of CSR in the annual reports were a poor proxy for fluctuations in volumes of CSR in all regularly produced Shell corporate reports. Therefore, it implies that if the researchers exclusively conduct the analysis of CSR disclosures via the content of the annual reports, it may not generate the validity of results since they ignore the analysis of CSR disclosures presented in other documents rather than the annual reports. However, most of these studies only analyze corporate reports, thereby arguably reasonably representative and selection of CSR analysis studies.

The term CSR can be regarded as an umbrella-term. The CSR literature begins with Bowen (1953) and proceeds through Friedman (1962), Carroll (1979) and Freeman (1984). The CSR disclosure process can be dispersed over a wide range of vehicles, including various media releases, annual reports, web sites, form 10-Ks, and stand-alone social and environmental reports (Mahoney et al, 2013). Many companies release information on their Web sites and in press releases, while a few larger companies put out dedicated corporate social responsibility or corporate citizenship reports¹⁰. Social and environmental disclosures occur in both hard copy- and web-based formats. Until to a few years ago, most social and environmental information was disclosed via traditional print documents (e.g. annual report or standalone print copies) or intermediaries (e.g., press releases by public media). The internet, a relatively new communication medium, offers as an alternative to traditional channels and allows firms to publicize more information less expensively and more quickly. However, the advent of the internet has led firms to reconsider their social and environmental reporting strategies, as well as their

¹⁰These reports are variously called such as Citizenship Report, Environment, Health and Safety Report, Sustainability Report, Corporate Responsibility Report, Environment Report, Social Responsibility Report, Community Report, Philanthropy Report, and Charitable Giving Report.

financial reporting because it offers much more flexibility than traditional disclosure vehicles for both the presentation and content of reporting. Nevertheless, traditional media (such as annual report and standalone report) carry a high degree of credibility among stakeholders because they tend to be assured or audited by others and any misrepresentation is liable under common law; the Internet lacks those features. Internet disclosure appears to be less relevant for financial analysts in setting earnings forecasts because they can find the necessary information in well-organized printed documents relatively easily, which shortens their prediction period. Most studies have solely examined only print-based annual report disclosure (e.g. Cormier et al., 2005; Branco and Rodrigues, 2008; Aerts and Cormier, 2009). A recent study examines the significant difference between how companies in various industry sectors deliver CSR information via the Web and annual reports (Sweeney and Coughan, 2008) but some researchers have preferred to examine stand-alone reports (e.g. Ho and Taylor, 2007; Dhaliwal, Li, Tsang, and Yang, 2011, Dhaliwal, Radhakrishnan, Tsang, and Yang, 2012; Mahoney et al., 2013). However, all of them only examine the disclosure quantities but not disclosure quality in standalone report. Using standalone as a disclosure vehicle can provide more room to release CSR disclosure information and allows this study for further investigation of its impact.

Gray et al (1995b) argue that it is impossible for researchers to identify and examine all visual and narrative communications as if they were limited resources. They thus examine only annual reports, the principal source of reporting. Similarly, this study confines itself to stand-alone reports (and avoids annual reports) because many corporations use them to disclose their corporate social responsibility information (Mahoney et al., 2013). They do this to perform two tasks—signaling and greenwashing. They provide two explanations for this, namely signalling and greenwashing. Signaling occurs when companies use stand-alone CSR reports to signal their superior commitment to and performance of CSR; thus, companies with stronger social and environmental performance are likely to issue stand-alone CSR reports (Berthelot et al., 2003; Al-Tuwaijri et al., 2004; Brammer and Pavelin, 2004; Cormier et al., 2004; Clarkson et al., 2008; Sikka, 2011, Coupland, 2006). Greenwashing occurs when companies use stand-alone reports to disclose CSR information that makes them appear to be good corporate citizens and thus improves stakeholders' socio-political perceptions of their social and environmental actions even if they are socially or environmentally weak (Patten, 2002; Clarkson et al., 2008). Cooper and Owen (2007) claim that more companies in the USA, Europe, and Australia proclaim their social responsibility credentials through stand-alone social and environmental reports.

More importantly, the number of CSR reports being issued is gradually increasing. In fact, more companies disclose CSR information through the stand-alone format than through annual reports in a recent decade. In a survey of CSR reporting practices, KPMG (2005) found that 71% of the FTSE 100 had issued social and environmental reports. Salterbaxter (2005), a consultancy company, found that the proportion of firms producing stand-alone CSR reports exceeded 80%. Furthermore, a 2011 KPMG International CSR survey found that 95% of the largest 250 international companies were issuing CSR information in a stand-alone format. This study examines the stand-alone report rather than annual reports because of the former's increasing importance; moreover, the annual report as already been widely studied. Stand-alone reports tend to contain more corporate CSR information than annual reports, thus reflecting a more thorough picture of CSR disclosure and quality.

As it is difficult for companies to disclose all their relevant information through annual reports, examining CSR disclosure quality through stand-alone reports likely better reflects corporate disclosure decisions regarding CSR. Financial analysts will look for CSR information from stand-alone reports rather than from annual reports as the former can provide them more information. An increasing amount of information is being provided through its CSR reports. This change implies that much information is no longer being disclosed in annual reports. Examining annual reports might lead to a misspecification problem (i.e. some CSR information disclosed have not been evaluated), as some of the CSR information disclosed might not be evaluated. Financial analysts can find CSR information

from stand-alone reports more easily than from annual reports since stand-alone report information is usually better organized and more thorough, while the CSR information disclosed in annual reports tends to be dispersed across the report. Hence, examining CSR disclosure decision as well as disclosure quality via the stand-alone disclosure vehicle be better reflecting the impact on financial analyst behaviour. CSR information concentrated in one document may be led to financial analysts greater attention. Besides, Stand-alone CSR reports are likely assured or audited by third parties whereas auditors have not duties on checking the social and environment information presented in annual reports, according to generally accepted accounting principles and accounting standards, unless such information has influenced corporate financial performance. So, this study considers both social and environmental disclosures as comprising of both quantitative and qualitative information that is released through standalone CSR report platforms.

Samples of this study

My research is to gather stand-alone corporate social responsibility reports of FT Global 500 as many as possible that were published covering period 2008 – 2012 and forecasting period 2009-2013. Further, this study uses sample firms from FT global 500 companies in different countries because one country samples are not sufficient to generalize the results. For instance, in the U.K. only 179 firms report 997 stand-alone CSR reports during period 1995 - 2007. Even in the U.S. 263 firms report only 1,172 stand-alone CSR reports during the same covering period of time (Dhaliwal et al, 2012). The major source of the FT global 500 company CSR reports comes from corporate websites, social funds, GRI databases and general search. Sample firms are required to have necessary Computstat for financial statement information and CSRP for share price data and Institutional Brokers' Estimate System (I/B/E/S) for analyst following, analyst annual earnings forecasts, and forecast dispersion data using the one-year ahead of the most recent forecasts a quarter before earnings announcement. For the testing period, this study follows *Behn, Choi and Kang (2008) in which analysts' EPS forecasts are used annual forecasts starting from 90 days before earning announcement and ending from 3 days before earning announcement. If there is more than one forecasts provided in that one year ahead of the testing period (the release CSR report year), it would use the recent one to calculate the forecast properties and number of financial analysts before earnings announcement in one year ahead of the CSR report release year.* In the robustness results, this study compares the mean of forecast accuracy, dispersion and number of financial analysts difference between this interest/case group (firms with release of standalone CSR disclosure, CSR reports assured by third parties, more number of pages of CSR reports, high social disclosure scores of CSR reports, high environmental disclosure scores of CSR reports and high total disclosure scores of CSR reports) and control groups (firms without release of standalone CSR disclosure, with CSR reports not assured by third parties, with less number of pages of CSR reports, with low social disclosure scores of CSR reports, with low environmental disclosure scores of CSR reports and with low total disclosure scores of CSR reports) and this study will eliminate the samples that lack of available necessary information of corporate share prices, corporate financial information and analyst following and forecast properties data in Compustat, CRSP and IBES databases. What is more, some companies' financial information has not fully covered by Compustat database, this the fact the fact that this study will also retrieve certain such data from Datastream database.

How to select Sample of hand collection data being used for testing the impact of the disclosure scores on number of financial analysts following firms with and without release of corporate social responsibility reports

This study examines the impact of CSR disclosure decision, quality and quantity on analyst behavior. The study's sampling companies were drawn fully from FT 500 global companies whose standalone reports came from various databases and general search a global corporate social responsibility (CR)

resources. Regarding testing the relationship between corporate disclosure scores and forecast properties and number of financial analysts, this study serially assigned codes into each company according to ascending corporate names and firm years and also using random generators to randomly select sampling firms from FT Global 500 companies so as to later collect social and environmental disclosure performance out of the corporate social responsibility reports using research instruments that developed based on GRI, prior academic studies and experience from experiments performed previously. The sample sizes is determined by the criteria of enough sample representative to forecast the whole population. Due to the fact that many FT Global 500 companies have not disclosed corporate social responsibility reports/ sustainability reports, social responsibility reports or other names that are suited for comparison of the mean of forecast accuracy, dispersion and number of financial analysts between high and low social, environmental and total disclosure scores of corporate social responsibility reports, this study will eliminate those companies without release of corporate social responsibility reports and compare those forecast properties and number of financial analysts of FT global companies with release of corporate social responsibility reports, thus the fact that the whole population for FT companies that disclosed corporate social responsibility reports are 895 firm years in which it has 229 companies with release of corporate social responsibility reports in 2012, 185 companies with release of corporate social responsibility reports in 2011, 178 companies with release of corporate social responsibility reports in 2010, 159 companies with release of corporate social responsibility reports in 2009 and 144 companies with release of corporate social responsibility reports in 2008. According to the above whole population of firm-year companies with release of corporate social responsibility reports across 5 year testing periods, 98 companies have been selected out of 229, 185, 178, 159 and 144 companies in 2012, 2011, 2010, 2009 and 2008 respectively and this study will collect all 89 items of the research instrument from each corporate social responsibility report of 98 randomly selected companies by random generator, thereby the fact regardless of number samples of companies and number samples of firm-year companies, both are sufficiently representative to the whole population of FT Global 500 companies with release of their corporate social responsibility reports. In conclusion, this study argues that the results using from 98 companies out of roughly 230 companies with disclosure of at least one of corporate social responsibility report within 5 year testing periods (i.e. 2008-2012) and 322 firm-year samples out of 889 firm year companies with disclosure of corporate social responsibility reports across 5 year testing periods are enough to predict the potential results of whole population of FT Global 500 companies with release of corporate social responsibility reports across 5 year testing periods (i.e. 2008 – 2012). This study also performed the univariate tests to find out the Pearson and Spearman correlation among main dependent, independent and control variables being used in different regression models in chapter 8 and 9, showing that number of pages of corporate social responsibility reports and various disclosure scores are highly correlated with each other within 99% confidential interval and 1% of significant error level. Since then, this study performed the comparison of data distribution on both whole population and samples of FT Global 500 companies, thereby showing that both of them are very similar each other. Further, the results also shows that the sample mean of number of pages of corporate social responsibility reports are within one standard deviation of mean of number of pages of corporate social responsibility reports, thereby conjecturing that the social, environmental and total disclosure scores of corporate social responsibility reports of the selected samples can represent various disclosure scores of corporate social responsibility reports of whole population of FT Global 500 companies. What is more, to prevent any self-selection bias of samples with release of corporate social responsibility reports despite of using random sample selection approach, this study will adopt one-way ANOVA to test difference of forecast accuracy, forecast dispersion and number of financial analysts between both high and low of corporate social, environmental and combined social and environmental disclosure scores of corporate social responsibility reports captured by research instruments of 89 items developed according to GRI, prior academic studies and pilot experiments before performance of this study in supplement with the multiple-variable regression models in chapter 8. The results of one-way ANOVA has been already shown in chapter 9 as robustness of results of this study.

Main independent Variables

My main variables are disclosure decision and disclosure quality. It will describe below how each of these variables is measured.

Estimation of Disclosure Decision

For the disclosure decision, this study follows **Brammer and Pavelin's (2006)** approach to distinguish the disclosure decision and disclosure quality. They use an indicator variable 1 if a company discloses any one of 6 environmental items as a measurement of firm "Disclosure Decision". Similar to them, this study's main variable, *DISCLOSURE DECISION*, is proxied by *STAND_ALONE*, an indicator variable showing whether the company issued at least one stand-alone CSR report during the year. 1 if firms disclose stand-alone CSR reports in particular year as interest group and 0 if firms do not disclose stand-alone CSR disclosure in particular year as control group because some firms disclose stand-alone CSR in some years but not to disclose such information in other years (results shown in chapter 9). So, it can argue that analyst coverage, forecasts accuracy and dispersion are likely affected by firms CSR disclosure decisions in different years (disclose or not disclose) due to more disclosed information. In the period firms with release of standalone CSR reports, analysts likely access much more CSR information to supplement with financial information available in financial reports, providing their annual earnings forecasts. What is more, in the period firms without release of CSR reports, it likely has less available information for their forecasts, resulting in less earnings forecast accuracy, large dispersed forecasts and few number of financial analysts.

Estimation of Disclosure quality: The *extent* approach

This study have followed prior works (e.g., **Guthrie & Parker, 1989; Patten, 1992, 1995; Gray, Kouhy, & Lavers, 1995b; Hackston and Milne, 1996; Gray et al., 2001; and Patten, 2002**) using the number of CSR report pages as a proxy for measuring CSR disclosure quality. More CSR content disclosed in CSR reports could be highly likely reflected in the number of pages. **Simnett et al. (2009)** argue that longer reports are likely to contain more information, and hence, then providing greater transparency (**Leuz and Schrand 2009**). However, this may still not ensure an accurate number of CSR pages that will reflect a firm's disclosure level and its quality. Thus, this study will use another proxy for CSR disclosure quality, namely corporate social and environmental disclosure scores captured by a 89-item research (the results shown in chapter 8 and 9).

Estimation of Disclosure quality: The *disclosure index/scores* approach

Alternatively, like earlier work in textual analysis which are applying "Classification schemes" (**Ernst and Ernst, 1978¹¹; Bowman and Haire, 1976; Trotman, 1979; Trotman and Bradley, 1981 and Guthrie, 1982; 1983**), this study will count the number of CSR items disclosed in CSR reports based on **Ho and Taylor's (2007)** list amended with GRI and other prior studies as a proxy for disclosure quality following **Ho and Taylor's (2007)** triple-bottom line approach to determine the disclosure quality. This approach is similar to **Wiseman's (1982)** textual analysis approach in which researchers check each item on the list to determine whether a company discloses such items in its reports. There are two main reasons for choosing their approach. First, this approach considers social, economic, and environmental

¹¹They include environment, energy, products/consumers, community, employee/human resources, fair business practices, general/other. They separate each area into monetary quantification, non-monetary quantification, both of them.

aspects, unlike other approaches that measure environmental or social disclosure practices alone (see Wiseman, 1982; Hackston and Milne, 1996; Gray et al., 2001; Patten, 2002; Christensen and Hughes II, 2004; Aerts and Cormier, 2009). Adams et al. (1998) also provide an approach to measure CSR reporting practices, but it does not cover all critical items of stakeholders (e.g., economics, customers, public sectors, and suppliers). Therefore, this approach is not as valid as Ho and Taylor's approach. Second, like Ho and Taylor's approach, it also examines the disclosure quality of stand-alone CSR reports. However, this approach still subjects the non-disclosing companies to an ordinary least squares (OLS) analysis to explain disclosure quality, resulting in unconvincing results. To migrate this problem, this study will score CSR disclosure quality from 89 to 267 using a 89-item research instrument, compared with Ho and Taylor's approach, this study provides more comprehensive CSR disclosure performance due to using more disclosure items in the research instrument to capture corporate CSR disclosure quality.

Regression Models

Analyst Coverage Determination Models: Linear Model

As number of financial analysts are very steady across years, in this study, financial analysts' coverage regression for all variables will firstly employ traditional regression linear model, by which it can determine the factors, affecting number of financial analysts for FT Global 500 companies. After verifying the model reliability using adjusted r square, r square, possibility for $F > F_0$ and chi-square, this model form is to satisfy above conditions, in which possibility of $F > F_0$ is significant within 99% confidential interval.

H1a. Analysts are more likely to follow for firms with providing stand-alone corporate social responsibility reports.

$$COV_{i,t} = \alpha + \beta_1 STAND_ALONE_{i,t-1} + \beta_2 MKTSIZE_{i,t-1} + \beta_3 STDROE_{i,t-1} + \beta_4 CORR_{i,t-1} + \beta_5 SALESCH_{i,t-1} + \beta_6 AR_{i,t-1} + \beta_7 INVPRICE_{i,t-1} + \beta_8 F_Accuracy_{i,t} + \beta_9 RETVAR_{i,t-1} + \beta_{10} RD_{i,t-1} + \beta_{11} EFFORT_{i,t} + \beta_{12} BROKER_{i,t} + \beta_{13} ROA_{i,t-1} + \beta_{14} PROA_{i,t-1} + Countries\ effects + Industry\ effects + Year\ effects + \epsilon_{i,t}$$

My main variable of interest is $STAND_ALONE_{i,t-1}$. It is predicted that β_1 is positive and significant.

H1b. Analysts are more likely to follow firms with providing more number of pages of stand-alone corporate social responsibility reports.

$$COV_{i,t} = \alpha + \beta_1 CSR_PAGE_{i,t-1} + \beta_2 MKTSIZE_{i,t-1} + \beta_3 STDROE_{i,t-1} + \beta_4 CORR_{i,t-1} + \beta_5 SALESCH_{i,t-1} + \beta_6 AR_{i,t-1} + \beta_7 INVPRICE_{i,t-1} + \beta_8 F_Accuracy_{i,t} + \beta_9 RETVAR_{i,t-1} + \beta_{10} RD_{i,t-1} + \beta_{11} EFFORT_{i,t} + \beta_{12} BROKER_{i,t} + \beta_{13} ROA_{i,t-1} + \beta_{14} PROA_{i,t-1} + Countries\ effects + Industry\ effects + Year\ effects + \epsilon_{i,t}$$

H1c. Analysts are more likely to follow firms with better social disclosure scores of stand-alone corporate social responsibility reports.

$$COV_{i,t} = \alpha + \beta_1 SOC_INDEX_{i,t-1} + \beta_2 MKTSIZE_{i,t-1} + \beta_3 STDROE_{i,t-1} + \beta_4 CORR_{i,t-1} + \beta_5 SALESCH_{i,t-1} + \beta_6 AR_{i,t-1} + \beta_7 INVPRICE_{i,t-1} + \beta_8 F_Accuracy_{i,t} + \beta_9 RETVAR_{i,t-1} + \beta_{10} RD_{i,t-1} + \beta_{11} EFFORT_{i,t} + \beta_{12} BROKER_{i,t} + \beta_{13} ROA_{i,t-1} + \beta_{14} PROA_{i,t-1} + Countries\ effects + Industry\ effects + Year\ effects + \epsilon_{i,t}$$

H1d. Analysts are more likely to follow firms with better environmental disclosure scores of stand-alone corporate social responsibility reports.

$$COV_{i,t} = \alpha + \beta_1 ENV_INDEX_{i,t-1} + \beta_2 MKTSIZE_{i,t-1} + \beta_3 STDROE_{i,t-1} + \beta_4 CORR_{i,t-1} + \beta_5 SALESCH_{i,t-1} + \beta_6 AR_{i,t-1} + \beta_7 INVPRICE_{i,t-1} + \beta_8 F_Accuracy_{i,t} + \beta_9 RETVAR_{i,t-1} + \beta_{10} LN RD_{i,t-1} + \beta_{11} EFFORT_{i,t} + \beta_{12} BROKER_{i,t} + \beta_{13} ROA_{i,t-1} + \beta_{14} PROA_{i,t-1} + Countries\ effects + Industry\ effects + Year\ effects + \epsilon_{i,t}$$

H1e. Analysts are more likely to follow firms with better social and environmental disclosure scores of stand-alone corporate social responsibility reports.

$$COV_{i,t} = \alpha + \beta_1 TOTAL_INDEX_{i,t-1} + \beta_2 MKTSIZE_{i,t-1} + \beta_3 STDROE_{i,t-1} + \beta_4 CORR_{i,t-1} + \beta_5 SALESCH_{i,t-1} + \beta_6 ARI_{i,t-1} + \beta_7 INVPRICE_{i,t-1} + \beta_8 F_Accuracy_{i,t} + \beta_9 RETVAR_{i,t-1} + \beta_{10} ORD_{i,t-1} + \beta_{11} EFFORT_{i,t} + \beta_{12} BROKER_{i,t} + \beta_{13} ROA_{i,t-1} + \beta_{14} PROA_{i,t-1} + Countries\ effects + Industry\ effects + Year\ effects + \epsilon_{i,t}$$

The main independent variables of interest are *CSR_PAGE*_{*i,t-1*}, *SOC_INDEX*_{*i,t-1*}, *ENV_INDEX*_{*i,t-1*} and *TOTAL_INDEX*_{*i,t-1*}. In model (1b to 1e), it is predicted that β_1 is positive and economically significant, implying that analysts are likely to follow firms with more number of pages of CSR reports, with better performance of social, environmental and total disclosure scores of corporate social responsibility reports.

H1f. Analysts are more likely to follow firms with stand-alone corporate social responsibility reports assured or audited by third party rather than firms with CSR reports but no assured or audited by third party.

$$COV_{i,t} = \alpha + \beta_1 CSR_AUDIT\&ASSURANCE_{i,t-1} + \beta_2 MKTSIZE_{i,t-1} + \beta_3 STDROE_{i,t-1} + \beta_4 CORR_{i,t-1} + \beta_5 SALESCH_{i,t-1} + \beta_6 ARI_{i,t-1} + \beta_7 INVPRICE_{i,t-1} + \beta_8 RETVAR_{i,t-1} + \beta_9 F_Accuracy_{i,t} + \beta_{10} ORD_{i,t-1} + \beta_{11} EFFORT_{i,t} + \beta_{12} BROKER_{i,t} + \beta_{13} ROA_{i,t-1} + \beta_{14} PROA_{i,t-1} + Countries\ effects + Industry\ effects + Year\ effects + \epsilon_{i,t}$$

Furthermore, this study checks each firm whether have found a third party to assure their CSR reports. It assigns 1 for a CSR report assured or audited by the third party in that particular year. Otherwise, zero value is assigned. The main variable of interest is *CSR_ASSURANCE*. It can be predicted that β_1 is positive and significant, indicating that analysts are more likely to follow firms with stand-alone CSR reports which are assured by the third party. It can be predicted that β_1 is positive and significant, indicating that analysts are more likely to follow firms with stand-alone CSR reports which are audited or assured by the professional.

Control Variables

Bhushan (1989b) argues that large firms are more likely to attract more analysts to follow because they can provide more brokerage and investment businesses for analysts' brokerage houses. Furthermore, large firms are more likely to be included in any market index, thus, attracting more analysts to provide forecasts because many insurance, investment and other funds are following the market indices to buy or sell firm stocks (**Arya and Mittendorf, 2007**). However, the theoretical predictions from **Fischer and Stocken (2010)** suggest that additional public information causes analysts to drop coverage. So, this study includes *MKTSIZE*_{*i,t-1*} variable, defined as the market value of the equity at the beginning of the year. Thus, it can be predicted to have a significantly positive or negative coefficient.

Following **Walther and Willis (1999)**, this study includes *SALECH*_{*i,t-1*}, and *ARI*_{*i,t-1*} as proxies for firm performance. *STDROE*_{*i,t-1*}, defined as the standard deviation of return-on-equity during the preceding a year period estimated by previous 5 year ROE, is predicted to have a positive coefficient. *CORR*_{*i,t-1*}, defined as the Pearson correlation between ROE and annual stock return in the preceding a year period estimated by last 5 year ROE and corporate stock return being computed by cumulative daily stock return, is predicted to have a positive coefficient. This variable is to measure the difficulty for analysts predicting firm earnings. Analysts are more likely to follow firms with more difficult to predict since they can generate more profits for their brokerage houses from forecasting and can access more private information from managers. **Bhushan (1989b)** argues that it is easier for analysts to predict future stock price for firms with higher return-earnings correlations. So, this study includes *INVPRICE*_{*i,t-1*} variable, defined as the inverse of stock price at the beginning of the year, predicted to have a positive coefficient. **Brennan and Hughes (1991)** argue that inverse of stock price proxies for the rate of the brokerage commission and the higher the brokerage commission can attract more analysts to follow the firm, so incorporating in this study.

Besides, this study also inserts $RETVAR_{i,t-1}$, defined as daily stock return variance estimated over the last year, predicted to have a positive coefficient with the main dependent variable. It is because [Bhushan \(1989b\)](#) documents that the degree of analyst following is positively related to return variability. [O'Brien and Bhushan \(1990\)](#) also find that the year-to-year change in analyst following is higher for firms who experience a decline in *return volatility*. [Alford and Berger \(1999\)](#) document that forecast accuracy and analyst following are endogenously determined, with greater accuracy associated with higher analyst following. So, this study incorporates $F_Accuracy_{i,t}$ in the model.

RDi_{t-1} , defined as the annual research and development expense divided by total assets/sales at the beginning of the fiscal year, is predicted to have a positive coefficient. [Barth et al. \(2001a\)](#) argue that intangible assets typically are not recognized, making financial statements less informative and providing greater incentive for analysts to follow firms with greater research and development expenses. Further, [Aboody and Lev \(2000\)](#) use research and development expenses out of total sales as a proxy for information asymmetry of firms, thus suggesting that analysts are more likely to follow firms with higher information asymmetry. $EFFORT_{i,t}$ is defined as the negative of the average number of firms followed by the firm's analysts in a particular year divided by the number of analysts covering the firm in that year. This variable captures the notion that if a particular firm requires more effort to cover it, then the firm's analysts will cover fewer firms ([Barth et al., 2001a](#)). $BROKER_{i,t}$ is defined as the average number of analysts employed by the brokerage houses that employ the firm's analysts. Larger brokerage houses have greater resources and can therefore follow more firms ([Jacob, Lys, and Neale, 1999](#); [Clement, 1999](#)). The inclusion of $BROKER_{i,t}$ in the model controls for cross-sectional difference in $EFFORT_{i,t}$ that is related to the size of the brokerage houses, thereby making the $EFFORT_{i,t}$ variable more effective ([Barth et al., 2001a](#)).

Finally, $ROA_{i,t-1}$ and $PROA_{i,t-1}$, defined earlier, control for the effect of profitability on analyst coverage. This study also controls country effects because samples include many countries over 30 in this study used because numerous studies report that institutional characteristics (i.e. country) influence the information environment across countries ([Ball et al., 2000b](#); [Rajan and Zingales, 2003](#)). [Ball et al \(2000b\)](#) provide evidence that stakeholder-oriented companies are likely to produce more corporate social responsibility reports. Other papers include [Cormier and Magnan \(1999\)](#) and [Berthelot et al \(2003\)](#). Further, [Dhaliwal et al \(2012\)](#) also find that firms in different countries affect the degrees of association between stand-alone CSR reports and analyst forecast accuracy. For instance, stand-alone CSR information can reduce more financial analyst forecast errors for firms in countries with more stakeholders oriented and firms in countries with more opaque financial disclosures. Therefore, to simplify the situation, this study incorporates country dummy variables in all regressions preventing this potential omitted correlated problem. More important, [O'Brien and Bhushan \(1990\)](#) that the year-to-year change in analyst following is higher for firms who operate in industries with regulated disclosures and who belong to industries with an increasing number of firms. [Bhushan \(1989b\)](#) documents that the degree of analyst following is negatively related to the number of *lines of business* of the firm. They choose two different proxies for the number of lines of business of a firm: (1) the number of three-digit SIC codes and (2) the number of four-digit SIC codes corresponding to the firm. This study also follows the second approach to incorporate a industry dummy variable based on four-digit SIC codes to control for industry effects in the regression models because my samples include more than 10 industries, in turn influencing the results. More importantly, CSR issuers likely concentrate in several industries, including utilities, transportation, chemicals and mining.

The table 1 provides the descriptive summaries, including means, median and standard derivation of all regression variables used in this paper regression dependent, independent and control variables. It also shows that number of samples of each variable will be used in OLS regressions. For the disclosure index (score) section, due to mainly collect data by hand rather than data collected from other sources,

the selected samples are roughly random and this study already performed the normal distribution of 322 samples representing approximately 40% of the whole population of FT Global 500 across testing periods. what is more, this study compares the normal distribution of number of pages of the whole population of FT Global 500 and the normal distribution of number of pages of the 322 samples of FT Global 500, showing that both the sample means of various disclosure scores are close to the population mean and the sample mean is within 0.5 standard deviation of the means of the whole population of number of pages variable, namely social, environmental and total disclosure scores of corporate social responsibility reports. To remediate the potential self-selection bias arising from sample selection of 322 firm-year corporations from the whole population of FT Global 500 corporations. Table 2 provides variable definitions used in above regression model specifications.

Descriptive Summary

Table 1: Distribution Statistics for Variables Used in Regressions, Pooled over Time. Sample of IBES, COMPUSTAT, DATASTREAM, WORLDScope and CRSP Firms from 2008–2012 (N = 2,500)

	N	Mean	Median	Standard Deviation
LNMKTSIZE	2413	18.22	17.60	1.88
SDROE5	2432	11.74	5.46	58.06
CORR	2256	0.04	0.01	0.52
SALESCH_SALES	2442	0.09	0.07	0.36
Abnormal_Return_value_weight	2404	0.01	0.00	0.30
INVPRICE	2407	0.09	0.02	0.89
ForecastAcc	2264	-33.89	-0.13	388.32
REVAR	2433	0.02	0.02	0.01
RD_Sales	2468	0.39	0.00	2.98
Efforts	2275	22.06	13.00	41.61
Broker_Rank	2277	838.83	894.68	156.29
ROA	2413	7.69	6.51	7.37
PROA	2402	8.04	6.90	7.48
Standalone_Dummy	2495	0.36	0.00	0.48
ABSEPSCH_P	2390	0.06	0.02	0.47
Ratio	2478	0.64	0.77	0.44
LOSS	2471	0.05	0.00	0.22
ADR_Dummy	2475	0.30	0.00	0.46
IFRS_Dummy	2485	0.39	0.00	0.49
LNHorizon	2270	3.63	3.64	0.40
COV_3monthbefore	2276	16.35	16.00	8.84
ABSEPSCH_EPS	2439	0.83	0.26	3.68
PE	2403	30.40	13.25	654.07
ABSSurprise_SALES	2451	0.07	0.03	0.14

LEVRatio	2462	68.25	0.71	627.65
Pages	889	77.12	66.00	51.69
Assurance_Dummy	2495	0.13	0.00	0.34
No_disclosure_items	322	50.00	51.00	13.54
Narrative_disclosure_items	322	29.24	25.00	18.57
Quantitative_disclosure_items	322	41.91	26.50	33.20
General_score	322	5.69	6.00	1.30
Product_score	322	12.61	12.00	2.77
Customer_score	322	6.28	6.00	1.79
Supply_score	322	1.78	1.00	0.87
Employee_score	322	27.45	28.00	5.46
Corporate_governance_score	322	9.02	9.00	2.30
Public_sectors_score	322	2.52	2.00	0.94
Communities_score	322	7.15	7.00	1.25
Integrity_and_ethics_score	322	1.58	2.00	0.60
Environmental_score	322	73.50	72.00	12.31
Totalscore	322	147.54	147.00	20.97
Social_score	322	74.07	75.00	11.08

Table 2

Variable Definitions

Abnormal_Return_value_weight/ AR	Firm i's compounded return over a one-year period ending in the third quarter of period t less the compounded return for the value weighted market index for the same period.
ABSEPSCH_P/ ACHEPS	The absolute value of annual change in earnings per share deflated by the beginning of fiscal year price.
ABSSurprise_SALES	The absolute value of annual change in earnings per share deflated by the beginning of fiscal year total sales.
ACHEPS	The absolute value of annual change in earnings per share deflated by the beginning of fiscal year price.
ADR_Dummy	Indicator that equals one if the firm is listed as ADR, and Zero otherwise.
Assurance_Dummy	Indicator that equals one if the CSR report is audited by big-4 or assured by independent third parties and other non-profit organizations, zero otherwise.
Broker_Rank	the percentile rank of broker size, measured by the number of analysts they hired in that particular year of forecast
CORR	Pearson correlation between stock return and ROE (return on equity) during the previous 5 years.
LNCOV_3monthbefore	Analyst coverage which equals the number of analysts covering the firm using the one-year-ahead EPS forecasts period starting a quarter before earnings announcement

	date that next year after the CSR report release date. So, the data is used available up to 30 June 2014.
COV_3monthbefore	the mean of number of financial analysts using the one-year-ahead EPS forecast a period starting a quarter before earnings announcement date that next year after the CSR report release date. So, the data is used available up to 30 June 2014.
EFFORT	The negative of the average number of firms followed by the firm's analysts in a particular year divided by the number of analysts covering the firm in that year.
ABSEPSCH_EPS	Absolute value of current year earnings per share minus last earnings per share, deflated by the last earnings per share.
EPSCH_EPS	Current year earnings per share minus last earnings per share, deflated by the last earnings per share.
IFRS_Dummy	Indicator that equals one if the firm adopts International Financial Reporting Standard, and zero otherwise.
INVPRICE	The inverse of stock price at the previous fiscal year end.
LEVRatio	Leverage, defined as total debt, divided by total asset, at the previous fiscal year end.
RETVAR	Return volatility, estimated as the standard deviation of daily stock returns in the previous year.
LNHorizon	Natural log of the mean value of analyst forecast horizon (the number of days between the forecast date and the earnings announcement date) a period starting a quarter before earnings announcement date that next year after the CSR report release date. So, the data is used with available up to 30 June 2014.
Horizon	the mean value of analyst forecast horizon (the number of days between the forecast date and the earnings announcement date) a period starting a quarter before earnings announcement date that next year after the CSR report release date. So, the data is used available up to 30 June 2014.
LNMKTSIZE	Natural log of market capitalization of total equity at the previous fiscal year end.
MKTSIZE	The market capitalization of total equity at the previous fiscal year end.
LOSS	Indicator that equals one if the firm is loss in the last fiscal year end.
Pages	Numbers of pages of CSR reports at period of t for firm i.
PE	Stock Price per share divided by the earnings per share at the last fiscal year end.
PROA	Net income deflated by total asset at last fiscal year at the last two year end.
RD_Sales	Research and development expense, divided by total sales at last fiscal year end.
Ratio	the ratio of the number of small positive earnings surprises (within 5% change) to the number of small negative earnings surprises (within 5% change) and assign to each country
RD_Sales	Research and development expense, divided by total sales at last fiscal year end.
REVAR	Return volatility, estimated as the standard deviation of daily stock returns in the previous year.
ROA	Net income deflated by total asset at the last fiscal year end.
SALESCH_SALES	change in annual net sales revenue for firm i in period t-1 divided by t-2 net sales
SDROE5	Standard deviation of return on equity (net income/common equity) in the previous 5 years.
Standalone_Dummy	Indicator that equals one if the observation of the firm issuing stand-alone CSR reports, and zero otherwise.
TL_TE	Total liabilities divided by total equity at the last fiscal year end.

No_Disclosure	Number of items in the disclosure quality checklist that the company has not disclosed in their corporate sustainability report
Narrative_Disclosure	Number of Narrative items that the company discloses in their corporate sustainability report.
Quantitive_Disclosure	Number of Quantitative items that the company discloses in their corporate sustainability report.
Total_Score	Total Disclosure Score for Corporate Sustainability Reports
Product_Score	The Product-related Dimension Disclosure Score in the Corporate Sustainability Reports. For this category, the value of this score for each firm is computed by counting the number of disclosure items reported by the firm within that category multiplied with the weighting of disclosure approaches (1 for no disclosure; 2 for narrative disclosure; 3 for quantitative disclosure)
Customer_Score	The Corporate Customer-related Dimension Disclosure Score in the Corporate Sustainability Reports. For this category, the value of this score for each firm is computed by counting the number of disclosure items reported by the firm within that category multiplied with the weighting of disclosure approaches (1 for no disclosure; 2 for narrative disclosure; 3 for quantitative disclosure).
Supply_Score	The Supplier-related Dimension Disclosure Score in the Corporate Sustainability Reports. For this category, the value of this score for each firm is computed by counting the number of disclosure items reported by the firm within that category multiplied with the weighting of disclosure approaches (1 for no disclosure; 2 for narrative disclosure; 3 for quantitative disclosure).
Employee_Score	The Employee-related Dimension Disclosure Score in the Corporate Sustainability Reports. For this category, the value of this score for each firm is computed by counting the number of disclosure items reported by the firm within that category multiplied with the weighting of disclosure approaches (1 for no disclosure; 2 for narrative disclosure; 3 for quantitative disclosure).
Corporate_Governance_Score	The Corporate Governance Dimension Disclosure Score in the Corporate Sustainability Reports. For this category, the value of this score for each firm is computed by counting the number of disclosure items reported by the firm within that category multiplied with the weighting of disclosure approaches (1 for no disclosure; 2 for narrative disclosure; 3 for quantitative disclosure).
Public_Sector_Score	The Corporate Public Dimension Disclosure Score in Corporate Sustainability Reports. For this category, the value of this score for each firm is computed by counting the number of disclosure items reported by the firm within that category multiplied with the weighting of disclosure approaches (1 for no disclosure; 2 for narrative disclosure; 3 for quantitative disclosure).
Communities_Score	The Corporate Community Contribution Dimension Disclosure Score in Corporate Sustainability Reports. For this category, the value of this score for each firm is computed by counting the number of disclosure items reported by the firm within that category multiplied with the weighting of disclosure approaches (1 for no disclosure; 2 for narrative disclosure; 3 for quantitative disclosure).
Integrity_Ethics_Score	The Integrity and Ethics Dimension Disclosure Score in Corporate Sustainability Reports. For this category, the value of this score for each firm is computed by counting the number of disclosure items reported by the firm within that category multiplied with the weighting of disclosure approaches (1 for no disclosure; 2 for narrative disclosure; 3 for quantitative disclosure).
Environmental_Score	The Environmental Dimension Disclosure Score in Corporate Sustainability Reports. For this category, the value of this score for each firm is computed by counting the number of disclosure items reported by the firm within that category multiplied with the weighting of disclosure approaches (1 for no disclosure; 2 for narrative disclosure; 3 for quantitative disclosure).

Social_Score The total Social Disclosure Score in corporate sustainability reports. For this category, the value of this score for each firm is summed by general score, product score, customer score, supply score, employee score, corporate governance score, public sector score, communities score, and integrity ethics score.

General_Score General Item Disclosure score in the Corporate Sustainability Reports

Multivariate Regression Results- Analyst Following Model Specifications

Table 5: The Impact of Corporate Disclosure Decision - issuing Standalone corporate sustainability report, on number of financial analysts a period starting a quarter before earnings announcement date: Evidence from Financial Times Global 500

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	-1964.376	435.209		-4.514	.000
	MKTSIZE	-2.336E-11	.000	-.041	-1.781	.075
	SDROE5	.004	.003	.031	1.423	.155
	CORR	.317	.383	.019	.826	.409
	SALESCH_SALES	-.291	.538	-.012	-.541	.589
	Abnormal_Return_value_weight	-2.244	.660	-.075	-3.398	.001
	INVPRICE	.284	1.423	.004	.199	.842
	ForecastAccy_3month_before	-.003	.001	-.131	-4.403	.000
	REVAR	105.655	21.560	.139	4.901	.000
	RD_Sales	.084	.092	.027	.919	.358
	Efforts	-.004	.005	-.019	-.839	.402
	Broker_Rank	.001	.002	.024	.868	.386
	ROA	.055	.044	.042	1.227	.220
	PROA	-.040	.042	-.032	-.939	.348
	SIC	-1.692E-5	.000	-.003	-.146	.884
	Country	.004	.001	.122	5.440	.000
	Year	.982	.216	.153	4.547	.000
	Standalone_Dummy	1.711	.407	.094	4.210	.000

a. Dependent Variable: COV_3monthbefore

$$COV_{i,t} = \alpha + \beta_1 STAND_ALONE_{i,t-1} + \beta_2 MKTSIZE_{i,t-1} + \beta_3 STDROE_{i,t-1} + \beta_4 CORR_{i,t-1} + \beta_5 SALESCH_{i,t-1} + \beta_6 AR_{i,t-1} + \beta_7 INVPRICE_{i,t-1} + \beta_8 F_Accuracy_{i,t} + \beta_9 RETVAR_{i,t-1} + \beta_{10} RD_Sales_{i,t-1} + \beta_{11} EFFORT_{i,t} + \beta_{12} BROKER_{i,t} + \beta_{13} ROA_{i,t-1} + \beta_{14} PROA_{i,t-1} + Countries\ effects + Industry\ effects + Year\ effects + \epsilon_{i,t}$$

The above regression result that shows financial analysts are likely following firms that issue standalone corporate sustainability report rather than those without issuance of corporate sustainability reports (t-value=4.210 and p-value=0.000 and N=2026), suggesting that financial analysts are using sustainability report and such information during forecasting process. $MKTSIZE_{i,t-1}$ is computed by the market value of corporate total equity t-1 (Bhushan (1989b)). $SDROE5_{i,t-1}$ is computed by the standard deviation of return on equity over the past 5 years. CORR is calculated by Pearson correlation between return on equity and return of stock return using corporate information over the past 5 years (Bhushan (1989b)). $SALESCH_SALES_{i,t-1}$ is computed by the change in sales between t-1 and t-2 deflated by sales at t-2 (Walther and Willis (1999)). $Abnormal_Return_value_weight_{i,t-1}$ is computed by Firm i's compounded return over a one-year period t-1 less the compounded return for the value weighted market index for the same period. $INVPRICE_{i,t-1}$ is computed by the inverse of stock price at the previous fiscal year ended at t-1 (Brennan and Hughes (1991)). $Forecast_Acc_{i,t-1}$ computation is the same as dependent variable. $REVAR_{i,t-1}$, Return volatility, is estimated as the standard deviation of daily stock returns in the previous year (Bhushan (1989b) and O'Brien and Bhushan (1990)). $RD_SALES_{i,t-1}$ is estimated by Research and development expense, divided by total sales at last fiscal year end (Barth et al. (2001a) and Aboody and Lev (2000)). Efforts is computed by The negative of the average number of firms followed by the firm's analysts in the forecasting year divided by the number of analysts covering the firm using the whole database firms (Barth et al., 2001a). $Broker_Rank_{i,t-1}$ is defined as the average number of analysts employed by the brokerage houses that employ the firm's analysts, following the approach of Jacob, Lys, and Neale (1999). $ROA_{i,t-1}$ is computed by Net income deflated by total asset at period of t-1 for firm i. $PROA_{i,t-1}$ is computed by Net income deflated by total asset at period of t-2 for firm i (Ball et al., 2000b; Rajan and Zingales, 2003). $Standalone_Dummy_{i,t-1}$ is assigned 1 for company that issue standalone corporate sustainability report for firm i at the period of time t-1. The dependent variable $COV_3monthbefore_{i,t-1}$ is computed by the mean of the most recent forecast by each financial analyst a period starting a quarter before earnings announcement date at t.

Table 6: The Impact of Corporate Disclosure Quantity- assurance of Corporate Sustainability Report, on number of financial analysts a period starting a quarter before earnings announcement date: Evidence from Financial Times Global 500

		Coefficients ^a				
		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		
Model		B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.
1	(Constant)	-1938.446	438.023		-4.425	.000
	MKTSIZE	-2.578E-11	.000	-.045	-1.960	.050
	SDROE5	.004	.003	.030	1.393	.164
	CORR	.209	.384	.012	.544	.586
	SALESCH_SALES	-.347	.540	-.014	-.643	.520
	Abnormal_Return_value_weight	-2.343	.662	-.079	-3.538	.000
	INVPRICE	.660	1.425	.010	.463	.643
	ForecastAccy_3month_before	-.003	.001	-.127	-4.240	.000
	REVAR	99.719	21.627	.131	4.611	.000
	RD_Sales	.104	.092	.034	1.134	.257
	Efforts	-.004	.005	-.017	-.753	.451
	Broker_Rank	.001	.002	.018	.665	.506
	ROA	.047	.045	.036	1.050	.294
	PROA	-.042	.042	-.033	-.983	.326
	SIC	-6.097E-5	.000	-.012	-.525	.599
	Country	.004	.001	.118	5.240	.000
	Year	.970	.217	.151	4.461	.000
	Assurance_Dummy	1.031	.587	.039	1.755	.079

a. Dependent Variable: COV_3monthbefore

$$COV_{i,t} = \alpha + \beta_1 CSR_AUDIT\&ASSURANCE_{i,t-1} + \beta_2 MKTSIZE_{i,t-1} + \beta_3 STDROE_{i,t-1} + \beta_4 CORR_{i,t-1} + \beta_5 SALESCH_{i,t-1} + \beta_6 AR_{i,t-1} + \beta_7 INVPRICE_{i,t-1} + \beta_8 F_Accuracy_{i,t} + \beta_9 RETVAR_{i,t-1} + \beta_{10} RD_Sales_{i,t-1} + \beta_{11} EFFORT_{i,t} + \beta_{12} BROKER_{i,t} + \beta_{13} ROA_{i,t-1} + \beta_{14} PROA_{i,t-1} + Countries\ effects + Industry\ effects + Year\ effects + \epsilon_{i,t}$$

The above results using the regression model shows that financial analysts are likely following firms that issue standalone CSR reports that also assured and audited by independent third parties and professional accounting firms, indicating that financial analysts likely partially use such information during their forecasting process, providing more accurate earnings forecasts. In turn, CSR information with assurance and auditing is one of determinants of the number of financial analysts (t-value=1.765, p-value=0.079). Other factors influencing financial analysts’ coverage includes corporate sizes, corporate financial and market performance, forecast accuracy and the corporate fixed effects, such as industry, country and year as above results shown.

Table 7: The Impact of Corporate Disclosure Quantity- proxied by the number of pages of Corporate Sustainability Report, on number of financial analysts a period starting a quarter before earnings announcement date: Evidence from Financial Times Global 500

		Coefficients ^a				
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	-1600.088	733.182		-2.182	.029
	MKTSIZE	3.507E-10	.000	.129	2.335	.020
	SDROE5	.004	.009	.014	.381	.703
	CORR	-.025	.596	-.002	-.042	.966
	SALESCH_SALES	-1.311	1.381	-.036	-.950	.343
	Abnormal_Return_value_weight	-2.071	1.084	-.070	-1.912	.056
	INVPRICE	-.114	1.533	-.003	-.074	.941
	ForecastAccy_3month_before	.001	.001	.020	.386	.700
	REVAR	127.215	36.369	.169	3.498	.000
	RD_Sales	-.200	.135	-.057	-1.480	.139
	Efforts	.002	.007	.011	.279	.780
	Broker_Rank	.002	.003	.037	.738	.461
	ROA	-.008	.083	-.006	-.091	.927
	PROA	.030	.079	.024	.383	.702
	SIC	.001	.000	.125	3.200	.001
	country	.006	.001	.197	5.222	.000
	year	.799	.364	.133	2.196	.028
	Pages	.019	.006	.117	3.237	.001

a. Dependent Variable: COV_3monthbefore

$$COV_{i,t} = \alpha + \beta_1 CSR_PAGE_{i,t-1} + \beta_2 MKTSIZE_{i,t-1} + \beta_3 STDROE_{i,t-1} + \beta_4 CORR_{i,t-1} + \beta_5 SALESCH_{i,t-1} + \beta_6 AR_{i,t-1} + \beta_7 INVPRICE_{i,t-1} + \beta_8 F_Accuracy_{i,t} + \beta_9 RETVAR_{i,t-1} + \beta_{10} RD_Sales_{i,t-1} + \beta_{11} EFFORT_{i,t} + \beta_{12} BROKER_{i,t} + \beta_{13} ROA_{i,t-1} + \beta_{14} PROA_{i,t-1} + Countries\ effects + Industry\ effects + Year\ effects + \epsilon_{i,t}$$

The above table shows that one of the determinants of number of financial analysts is number of pages of corporate social responsibility information provided by firms. More financial analysts are likely following firms with issuance of more number of pages of CSR reports, suggesting such social and environmental information is useful for financial analysts or to another say, such information can affect corporate future financial performance, thereby capturing up them analyzing them (t-value=3.237, p-value=0.001). In above regression model shown, corporate sizes, Abnormal_Return and VAR on return on equity are likely influential factor to determine number of financial analysts, thereby the fact that

financial analysts’ coverage is a function of corporate sizes, corporate financial and market performance and the fixed effects.

Table 8: The Impact of Corporate Disclosure Quantity- Social Index of Corporate Sustainability Report, on number of financial analysts a period starting a quarter before earnings announcement date: Evidence from Financial Times Global 500

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	-2892.647	1206.344		-2.398	.017
	MKTSIZE	-2.665E-10	.000	-.034	-.304	.761
	SDROE5	.007	.009	.048	.795	.427
	CORR	1.590	.906	.114	1.754	.081
	SALESCH_SALES	-1.218	2.129	-.036	-.572	.568
	Abnormal_Return_value_weight	-1.144	1.811	-.040	-.631	.528
	INVPRICE	-.883	1.554	-.037	-.568	.571
	ForecastAccy_3month_before	.024	.096	.027	.251	.802
	REVAR	181.122	56.243	.276	3.220	.001
	RD_Sales	.236	.625	.033	.378	.705
	Efforts	-.005	.016	-.026	-.292	.771
	Broker_Rank	.002	.004	.038	.435	.664
	ROA	-.267	.141	-.186	-1.895	.059
	PROA	.017	.141	.012	.119	.905
	SIC	-8.463E-5	.000	-.019	-.277	.782
	Country	.002	.002	.075	1.136	.257
	Year	1.443	.598	.268	2.411	.017
	Social_score	.074	.042	.107	1.741	.083

a. Dependent Variable: COV_3monthbefore

$$COV_{i,t} = \alpha + \beta_1 SOC_INDEX_{i,t-1} + \beta_2 MKTSIZE_{i,t-1} + \beta_3 STDROE_{i,t-1} + \beta_4 CORR_{i,t-1} + \beta_5 SALESCH_{i,t-1} + \beta_6 AR_{i,t-1} + \beta_7 INVPRICE_{i,t-1} + \beta_8 F_Accuracy_{i,t} + \beta_9 RETVAR_{i,t-1} + \beta_{10} RD_Sales_{i,t-1} + \beta_{11} EFFORT_{i,t} + \beta_{12} BROKER_{i,t} + \beta_{13} ROA_{i,t-1} + \beta_{14} PROA_{i,t-1} + Countries\ effects + Industry\ effects + Year\ effects + \epsilon_{i,t}$$

The table 6 shows the result that the impact of social information in standalone CSR on number of financial analysts and both of them are statistically positively correlated with each other (t-value=1.741, p-value=0.083). In turn, social responsibility disclosure is one of the determinant factor affecting financial analysts’ coverage. Other factors influencing the number of financial analysts including

correlation between both return on ROE and return on equity, VAR on return on equity, corporate financial performance, measured by return on assets and fixed effects.

Table 9: The Impact of Corporate Disclosure Quantity- Environmental Index of Corporate Sustainability Report, on number of financial analysts a period starting a quarter before earnings announcement date: Evidence from Financial Times Global 500

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Coefficients		
				Beta		
1	(Constant)	-2706.968	1205.622		-2.245	.026
	MKTSIZE	-1.981E-10	.000	-.025	-.226	.822
	SDROE5	.007	.009	.044	.726	.469
	CORR	1.377	.905	.099	1.522	.129
	SALESCH_SALES	-1.122	2.134	-.033	-.526	.600
	Abnormal_Return_value_weight	-1.245	1.815	-.043	-.686	.493
	INVPRICE	-.523	1.548	-.022	-.338	.736
	ForecastAccy_3month_before	.032	.096	.035	.329	.742
	REVAR	171.041	55.956	.261	3.057	.002
	RD_Sales	.132	.623	.018	.212	.833
	Efforts	-.005	.016	-.025	-.288	.773
	Broker_Rank	.002	.004	.038	.431	.667
	ROA	-.285	.143	-.198	-1.995	.047
	PROA	.020	.141	.014	.141	.888
	SIC	-1.784E-5	.000	-.004	-.056	.955
	Country	.002	.002	.064	.976	.330
	Year	1.352	.598	.251	2.259	.025
	Environmental_score	.051	.041	.081	1.512	.193

a. Dependent Variable: COV_3monthbefore

$$COV_{i,t} = \alpha + \beta_1 ENV_INDEX_{i,t-1} + \beta_2 MKTSIZE_{i,t-1} + \beta_3 STDROE_{i,t-1} + \beta_4 CORR_{i,t-1} + \beta_5 SALESCH_{i,t-1} + \beta_6 AR_{i,t-1} + \beta_7 INVPRICE_{i,t-1} + \beta_8 F_Accuracy_{i,t} + \beta_9 RETVAR_{i,t-1} + \beta_{10} RD_Sales_{i,t-1} + \beta_{11} EFFORT_{i,t} + \beta_{12} BROKER_{i,t} + \beta_{13} ROA_{i,t-1} + \beta_{14} PROA_{i,t-1} + Countries\ effects + Industry\ effects + Year\ effects + \epsilon_{i,t}$$

For the impact of environmental dimension disclosures of corporate sustainability reports on the number of financial analysts, the table 9 shows the insignificant result (t-value=1.512 and p-value=0.193 and N=273), indicating that the environmental activities are not likely affecting financial analysts in decision following the firms but this result is still subject to the firm-year observations under examination. Uncertainty of corporate financial performance (i.e. $REVAR_{i,t-1}$) can also attract more financial analysts to follow the firms that issue of corporate social responsibility reports due to the

higher uncertainty of corporate financial performance can likely provide potential profit to financial analysts' brokerage firms (t-value=3.057 and p-value=0.002 and N=273). Corporate financial performance and the fixed effects are also determinants of financial analysts' coverage in the Log-Lin regression models.

Table 10: The Impact of Corporate Disclosure Quantity- Total Index of Corporate Sustainability Report, on number of financial analysts a period starting a quarter before earnings announcement date: Evidence from Financial Times Global 500

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	-2795.315	1204.446		-2.321	.021
MKTSIZE	-2.343E-10	.000	-.030	-.267	.790
SDROE5	.007	.009	.046	.773	.440
CORR	1.470	.903	.105	1.629	.105
SALESCH_SALES	-1.170	2.131	-.034	-.549	.583
Abnormal_Return_value_weight	-1.185	1.812	-.041	-.654	.514
INVPRICE	-.694	1.547	-.029	-.449	.654
ForecastAccy_3month_before	.027	.096	.030	.282	.778
REVAR	176.552	56.063	.269	3.149	.002
RD_Sales	.186	.623	.026	.298	.766
Efforts	-.005	.016	-.025	-.290	.772
Broker_Rank	.002	.004	.040	.459	.647
ROA	-.281	.142	-.196	-1.982	.049
PROA	.019	.141	.013	.133	.894
SIC	-2.922E-5	.000	-.007	-.094	.925
Country	.002	.002	.069	1.048	.295
Year	1.395	.598	.259	2.334	.020
Totalscore	.036	.023	.100	1.641	.098

a. Dependent Variable: COV_3monthbefore

$$COV_{i,t} = \alpha + \beta_1 TOTAL_INDEX_{i,t-1} + \beta_2 MKTSIZE_{i,t-1} + \beta_3 STDROE_{i,t-1} + \beta_4 CORR_{i,t-1} + \beta_5 SALESCH_{i,t-1} + \beta_6 AR_{i,t-1} + \beta_7 INVPRICE_{i,t-1} + \beta_8 F_Accuracy_{i,t} + \beta_9 RETVAR_{i,t-1} + \beta_{10} RD_Sales_{i,t-1} + \beta_{11} EFFORT_{i,t} + \beta_{12} BROKER_{i,t} + \beta_{13} ROA_{i,t-1} + \beta_{14} PROA_{i,t-1} + Countries\ effects + Industry\ effects + Year\ effects + \epsilon_{i,t}$$

The total score of corporate social responsibility report is marginally statistically positively correlated with corporate number of financial analysts due to the fact that financial analysts are likely following more for firms with higher disclosure score and better social and environmental performance (t-value =1.641 and p-value=0.098 and N=273). As does above results, *REVAR* *i,t-1* is significantly positively correlated with number of financial analysts covering the firms that issue corporate social responsibility report with better total performance using the self- developed research instrument to capture corporate social and environment

al disclosure and activity performance. Other factors determining the financial analysts' coverage, including corporate financial and market performance, correlation between return on equity and return on stock return and the fixed effects.

Conclusions:

The results show that firms issue stand-alone CSR reports can attract more financial analysts following the firms. When firms with thirty party assuring their CSR reports also attract more financial analysts following themselves. When firms with higher CSR disclosure quantity proxied by number of pages of CSR reports, they will have higher financial analyst coverage. Finally, firms with better social and environmental disclosure quality will attract more financial analysts following the firms.

Recommendations:

The future research can follow up this study to investigate the impact of CSR disclosure quantity and quality on capital markets due to such disclosure can influence financial analysts, one of capital market participants. The results on this paper can help regulators to decide whether mandate firms issue stand-alone CSR reports or audit their CSR reports to help financial analysts using those reports. What is more, the results shows better disclosure index on social and environment in CSR reports will attract more financial analysts following provide more accuracy of their forecasts. So, regulators can decide whether to mandate firms to disclose more social and environmental issues to financial analysts and investors.

Robustness

After controlling the heteroscedasticity inconsistent standard error and auto correlation problems using Newey-West corrected standard error regression approach (1994) in which they recommend approaches to revise the standard errors of each explanatory variables in the regression so as to ensure the regression model can provide relatively reliable results to test the relationship X's and Y.

Table 11. Newey West regression model: The impact of corporate social disclosure decision on number of financial analysts

Dependent Variable: COV_3MONTHBEFORE

Method: Generalized Method of Moments

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	-2086.734	483.8742	-4.312554	0.0000
MKTSIZE	-2.31E-11	7.83E-12	-2.953802	0.0032
SDROE5	0.004325	0.001351	3.202107	0.0014
CORR	0.332729	0.521228	0.638356	0.5233
SALESCH_SALES	-0.230596	0.707388	-0.325982	0.7445
ABNORMAL_RETURN	-2.617818	0.618849	-4.230139	0.0000
INVPRICE	0.253555	1.022637	0.247942	0.8042
REVAR	111.7810	30.56221	3.657491	0.0003

RD_SALES	0.083400	0.145055	0.574958	0.5654
EFFORTS	-0.003476	0.003813	-0.911727	0.3620
BROKER_RANK	0.001219	0.001781	0.684710	0.4936
ROA	0.059349	0.046274	1.282558	0.1998
PROA	-0.038822	0.037773	-1.027786	0.3042
FORECASTACCY_3MONTH_BEFO	-0.002818	0.000795	-3.547094	0.0004
SIC	-1.61E-05	0.000220	-0.073064	0.9418
COUNTRY	0.003876	0.001174	3.300365	0.0010
YEAR	1.043110	0.240061	4.345179	0.0000
STANDALONE_DUMMY	1.701949	0.626860	2.715038	0.0067
<hr/>				
R-squared	0.066389	Mean dependent var	16.52542	
Adjusted R-squared	0.058563	S.D. dependent var	8.787638	
S.E. of regression	8.526440	Sum squared resid	147436.0	
Durbin-Watson stat	0.756762	J-statistic	2.93E-30	

After adjusting the standard errors of various independent variables, financial analysts are more likely following firms that issue standalone corporate social responsibility reports, when compared with those firms that do not issue any standalone corporate social responsibility reports in that particular year (p-value=0.0067), significant within 99% confident interval. Other control variables that are correlated with main dependent variables in above regression model specification, i.e. number of financial analysts, including the corporate characteristics, corporate financial performance, measured by standard deviation of return on equity over the past 5 years, corporate stock market performance, measured by the absolute value of the difference in stock price performance and market index performance, and corporate fixed effects (all of them are statistically significant).

Table 12. Newey West regression model: The impact of corporate social disclosure quality, measured by standalone CSR reports assured or audited by third parties or professional accounting firms on number of financial analysts

Dependent Variable: COV_3MONTHBEFORE

Method: Generalized Method of Moments

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	-2065.330	485.9920	-4.249720	0.0000
MKTSIZE	-2.55E-11	7.84E-12	-3.253520	0.0012
SDROE5	0.004246	0.001342	3.164393	0.0016
CORR	0.226976	0.529640	0.428548	0.6683
SALESCH_SALES	-0.283885	0.748467	-0.379288	0.7045
ABNORMAL_RETURN	-2.718273	0.625078	-4.348697	0.0000

INVPRICE	0.629119	1.005991	0.625372	0.5318
REVAR	106.0536	30.66869	3.458042	0.0006
RD_SALES	0.103175	0.140881	0.732354	0.4640
EFFORTS	-0.003077	0.004024	-0.764871	0.4444
BROKER_RANK	0.000899	0.001786	0.503245	0.6148
ROA	0.051716	0.046110	1.121583	0.2622
PROA	-0.040737	0.038037	-1.070982	0.2843
FORECASTACCY_3MONTH_BEFO	-0.002722	0.000773	-3.520257	0.0004
SIC	-5.98E-05	0.000220	-0.271765	0.7858
COUNTRY	0.003756	0.001165	3.223726	0.0013
YEAR	1.033058	0.241090	4.284939	0.0000
ASSURANCE_DUMMY	1.027426	0.742626	1.383504	0.1667
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R-squared	0.059726	Mean dependent var		16.52542
Adjusted R-squared	0.051844	S.D. dependent var		8.787638
S.E. of regression	8.556812	Sum squared resid		148488.2
Durbin-Watson stat	0.753596	J-statistic		1.08E-31

Firms that assure their standalone corporate social responsibility reports are likely affecting number of financial analysts following those firms due to the fact the above assurance_dummy variable is marginally positively correlated with number of financial analysts in the above regression model specification, implying that financial analysts more prefer firms that provide more creditable social and environmental information in standalone disclosure approach (p-value=0.1667) after adjusting the inconsistent variance of standard errors of all independent variables and autocorrelation. Other control variables likely affect number of financial analysts in the regression model specification, including corporate sizes, corporate financial performance, measured by standard deviation of return on equity over the past 5 years, corporate market return on their stocks, VAR on return on equity, time fixed effects.

Table 13. Newey West regression model: The impact of corporate social disclosure quantity, measured by number of pages of standalone CSR reports, on number of financial analysts

Dependent Variable: COV_3MONTHBEFORE

Method: Generalized Method of Moments

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	-1741.333	784.9434	-2.218419	0.0268
MKTFSIZE	3.53E-10	1.90E-10	1.857819	0.0636
SDROE5	0.003897	0.004562	0.854362	0.3932
CORR	-0.025123	0.728323	-0.034494	0.9725

SALESCH_SALES	-1.261847	1.019338	-1.237909	0.2162
ABNORMAL_RETURN	-2.478367	0.839437	-2.952417	0.0033
INVPRICE	-0.165581	1.085103	-0.152595	0.8788
REVAR	134.5518	39.15787	3.436137	0.0006
RD_SALES	-0.204171	0.097989	-2.083618	0.0375
EFFORTS	0.002409	0.005148	0.467992	0.6399
BROKER_RANK	0.001769	0.002531	0.698828	0.4849
PROA	0.022126	0.062078	0.356422	0.7216
ROA	0.007501	0.083583	0.089741	0.9285
FORECASTACCY_3MONTH_BEFO	0.000552	0.001346	0.409831	0.6821
SIC	0.000622	0.000328	1.898680	0.0580
COUNTRY	0.005555	0.001451	3.827725	0.0001
YEAR	0.869101	0.389497	2.231341	0.0260
PAGES	0.018785	0.007962	2.359437	0.0186
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R-squared	0.101818	Mean dependent var	17.54768	
Adjusted R-squared	0.080492	S.D. dependent var	8.297983	
S.E. of regression	7.957017	Sum squared resid	45332.91	
Durbin-Watson stat	0.831912	J-statistic	1.54E-33	

The above table shows that firms with better corporate disclosure quantity can affect analysts to decide to follow them as the main independent variable, i.e. number of pages of standalone corporate social responsibility reports is statistically positively significantly correlated with number of financial analysts (p-value=0.0186), suggesting that the financial analysts more likely following firms that issue more number of pages of standalone CSR reports so as to access more corporate social and environmental and other non-financial financial information during their earnings forecasting process. Corporate characteristics, corporate business structures and fixed effects can also determine analysts' coverage in that particular year.

Table 14. Newey West regression model: The impact of corporate social disclosure scores on number of financial analysts

Dependent Variable: COV_3MONTHBEFORE

Method: Generalized Method of Moments

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	-2888.318	1143.693	-2.525430	0.0122
MKTSIZE	-2.92E-10	1.25E-09	-0.233324	0.8157
SDROE5	0.007813	0.005561	1.404804	0.1613
CORR	1.545112	1.048417	1.473757	0.1418

SALESCH_SALES	-1.128887	1.706591	-0.661487	0.5089
ABNORMAL_RETURN	-2.025553	1.394144	-1.452900	0.1475
INVPRICE	-0.951955	1.114679	-0.854017	0.3939
REVAR	181.8403	50.20104	3.622242	0.0004
RD_SALES	0.242117	0.675116	0.358630	0.7202
EFFORTS	-0.004650	0.011625	-0.399997	0.6895
BROKER_RANK	0.001436	0.003825	0.375314	0.7077
ROA	-0.238508	0.153620	-1.552582	0.1217
PROA	-0.003910	0.152307	-0.025675	0.9795
FORECASTACCY_3MONTH_BEFO	0.023067	0.075235	0.306592	0.7594
SIC	-7.62E-05	0.000369	-0.206728	0.8364
COUNTRY	0.001930	0.001889	1.021253	0.3081
YEAR	1.440992	0.567276	2.540196	0.0117
SOCIAL_SCORE	0.073154	0.051386	1.423607	0.1558
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R-squared	0.127951	Mean dependent var	17.96377	
Adjusted R-squared	0.070490	S.D. dependent var	7.650463	
S.E. of regression	7.375896	Sum squared resid	14036.19	
Durbin-Watson stat	0.900676	J-statistic	0.000000	

The above table shows that the *social_score* variable is positively correlated with firms that followed by more number of financial analysts although it is not statistically significant within 90% confident interval (p-value=0.1558), indicating that financial analysts will follow FT Global 500 firms that do better in their own social responsibility activities since they can provide more information to them to forecast corporate earnings.

Table 15. Newey West regression model: The impact of corporate environmental disclosure scores on number of financial analysts

Dependent Variable: COV_3MONTHBEFORE

Method: Generalized Method of Moments

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	-2713.440	1159.433	-2.340316	0.0200
MKTSIZE	-2.24E-10	1.30E-09	-0.172926	0.8628
SDROE5	0.007174	0.005421	1.323348	0.1869
CORR	1.337769	1.047560	1.277033	0.2027
SALESCH_SALES	-1.035713	1.668431	-0.620771	0.5353
ABNORMAL_RETURN	-2.075511	1.420736	-1.460870	0.1453

INVPRICE	-0.592194	1.213434	-0.488031	0.6259
REVAR	172.1183	51.25347	3.358178	0.0009
RD_SALES	0.138556	0.692535	0.200070	0.8416
EFFORTS	-0.004661	0.011414	-0.408335	0.6834
BROKER_RANK	0.001436	0.004031	0.356196	0.7220
ROA	-0.256102	0.151752	-1.687638	0.0927
PROA	-8.11E-06	0.159661	-5.08E-05	1.0000
FORECASTACCY_3MONTH_BEFO	0.030328	0.078089	0.388378	0.6981
SIC	-1.12E-05	0.000384	-0.029224	0.9767
COUNTRY	0.001656	0.001892	0.875503	0.3821
YEAR	1.354949	0.575067	2.356158	0.0192
ENVIRONMENTAL_SCORE	0.050026	0.051195	0.977165	0.3294
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R-squared	0.122810	Mean dependent var	17.96377	
Adjusted R-squared	0.065011	S.D. dependent var	7.650463	
S.E. of regression	7.397602	Sum squared resid	14118.93	
Durbin-Watson stat	0.862999	J-statistic	0.000000	

Firms that issue better environmental disclosure performance of standalone CSR reports are likely capturing up more number of financial analysts to follow them although the above result is not statistically significant within 90% confidential interval. However, the positive coefficient correlation of *ENVIRONMENTAL_SCORE* indicates that financial analysts likely following firms with better environmental disclosure scores, compared with firms with poor of environmental disclosure scores (p-value=0.3294).

Table 16. Newey West regression model: The impact of corporate social and environmental disclosure scores on number of financial analysts

Dependent Variable: COV_3MONTHBEFORE

Method: Generalized Method of Moments

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	-2795.723	1153.112	-2.424504	0.0160
MKTSIZE	-2.60E-10	1.27E-09	-0.204372	0.8382
SDROE5	0.007607	0.005483	1.387178	0.1666
CORR	1.427947	1.038383	1.375165	0.1703
SALESCH_SALES	-1.082909	1.670716	-0.648170	0.5175
ABNORMAL_RETURN	-2.039188	1.406208	-1.450132	0.1482
INVPRICE	-0.762565	1.177679	-0.647516	0.5179
REVAR	177.4123	50.72550	3.497497	0.0006

RD_SALES	0.191495	0.682182	0.280710	0.7792
EFFORTS	-0.004645	0.011547	-0.402270	0.6878
BROKER_RANK	0.001537	0.003927	0.391366	0.6958
ROA	-0.252386	0.151655	-1.664209	0.0973
PROA	-0.001452	0.156504	-0.009277	0.9926
FORECASTACCY_3MONTH_BEF				
O	0.025915	0.077149	0.335913	0.7372
SIC	-2.17E-05	0.000376	-0.057802	0.9540
COUNTRY	0.001777	0.001894	0.938454	0.3489
YEAR	1.394955	0.571886	2.439221	0.0154
TOTALSCORE	0.036018	0.028585	1.260036	0.2088
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R-squared	0.126009	Mean dependent var	17.96377	
Adjusted R-squared	0.068420	S.D. dependent var	7.650463	
S.E. of regression	7.384104	Sum squared resid	14067.45	
Durbin-Watson stat	0.882069	J-statistic	7.48E-33	

After revising the variances of standard error terms of all independent variables, financial analysts likely following firms with better social and environmental performance reflected in standalone corporate social responsibility reports (p-value=0.2088), suggesting that if firms can do better in CSR or invest more corporate social and environmental activities, financial analysts are likely using more such information for their forecasting, thereby providing more accurate results in the regression models.

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